

Stakeholder mapping and initial engagement plan

Deliverable 6.1

Date: 27.03.2025

Authors (Organisation): Luca E. Sander
(CSCP), Charis Hoffmann (CSCP), Nora
Brüggemann (CSCP), Relana Lutz (CSCP),
Lily Pepper (CSCP)

LEGAL DISCLAIMER

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101181994.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

© PRECIOUS. Copies of this publication – also of extracts thereof – may only be made with reference to the publisher.

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	PRECIOUS
Project Title	Addressing the Environmental Impacts of Food Loss And Waste Prevention And Its Rebound Effects
Project Number	101181994
Project Coordinator	Deitze Otaduy (deitze.otaduy@deusto.es)
Project Duration	01/10/2024 – 30/09/2028

Deliverable title	Stakeholder mapping and initial engagement plan
Deliverable Num.	D6.1
Work Package	6
Dissemination level	Public
Lead beneficiary	Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP)
Contributing beneficiaries	CluBE, ASINCAR, Vegalsa, UNIMOS Alliance, INNOMINE, Agrifood Lithuania
Authors	Charis Hoffmann, Luca E. Sander, Relana Lutz, Lily Pepper (all CSCP)
Internal reviewers	EIT Food, Vegalsa, Greenovate! Europe
External peer reviewers	N/A
Document approval	
Submission deadline	31/03/2025
Actual Submission date	28/03/2025

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author [Organization]	Description of the main changes
1	10/03/25	Charis Hoffmann, Luca E. Sander, Relana Lutz, Lily Pepper [all CSCP]	First version, submitted to three project partners for internal review (ASINCAR, Greenovate! Europe (G!E), EIT Food). The first version included an initial version of the graphs, descriptions to all stakeholder mapping activities, and the first draft of the initial engagement plan. Luca E. Sander was responsible for the data analysis, the design and writing for the stakeholder analysis sections of the 2 Use Case locations and 3 Co-creation and Replication Nodes. Charis Hoffmann led the European stakeholder mapping, and the design and writing of the initial engagement plan. Relana Lutz and Lily Pepper assisted the writing process. Nora Brüggemann and Jennifer Wiegard provided CSCP-internal feedback, which was incorporated to consolidate Version 1.
2	21/03/25	Charis Hoffmann, Luca E. Sander, Relana Lutz [all CSCP]	The second version incorporated the feedback, provided by Cristina Viera (ASINCAR), Marcell Boviz (G!E), and Leticia López (EIT Food). Their contributions resulted in an improved colour palette, increased readability of graphs, improved length and structure of longer paragraphs, correction of spelling mistakes, and improvements to the initial engagement plan. Version 2 was then sent to all project partners, to collect further recommendations for improvements by the consortium.
3	28/03/25	Charis Hoffmann, Luca E. Sander [both CSCP]	Version 3 responded to feedback by the project consortium. Feedback was provided by Manuel Amador (DEUSTO), Olga Dziabenko (DEUSTO), Deitze Otaduy (DEUSTO), Panagiotis Fragkos (E3M), Theodora Kalea (CluBE), Marcell Boviz (G!E), Rie Larsen (YAGHMA). Their Feedback included: improvements to the formatting in line with the PRECIOUS visual identity, revisions to the executive summary including content and structure, final adjustments of graphs, requests for additional information on the links to other work packages, screening of remaining grammar and spelling mistakes, requests for additional information in individual mapping results, request to provide further details to the revision history. Version 3 integrated all recommendations into the final version of the deliverable.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Executive Summary.....9

 1.1. Project Overview9

 1.2. Deliverable Summary9

 How to read this document.....10

2. Introduction11

 2.1. Planned PRECIOUS Multi-Stakeholder Engagement Formats: CoPs and CRNs11

 2.2. Objective of PRECIOUS Stakeholder Mapping12

 2.3. Suggested PRECIOUS Initial Engagement Plan.....12

3. Stakeholder mapping13

 3.1. Stakeholder analysis methodology13

 3.2. Greek CoP.....14

 3.2.1. Stakeholder Composition.....15

 3.2.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups16

 3.2.3. Relations to Mapped Stakeholders18

 3.2.4. Key Motivators of Stakeholder Groups.....19

 3.2.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups.....21

 3.3. Spanish CoP.....23

 3.3.1. Stakeholder Composition.....23

 3.3.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups24

 3.3.3. Relations to Mapped Stakeholders29

 3.3.4. Key Motivators of Stakeholder Groups.....30

 3.3.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups.....32

 3.4. Hungarian CRN34

 3.4.1. Stakeholder Composition.....34

 3.4.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups35

 3.4.3. Relations to Stakeholders39

 3.4.4. Key Motivators of Stakeholder Groups.....41

 3.4.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups.....43

 3.5. Lithuanian CRN.....45

 3.5.1. Stakeholder Composition.....45

 3.5.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups46

 3.5.3. Relations to Stakeholders49

 3.5.4. Key Motivators of Supply Groups.....51

 3.5.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups.....52

 3.6. Polish CRN54

 3.6.1. Stakeholder Composition.....54

- 3.6.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups55
- 3.6.3. Relations to Stakeholders58
- 3.6.4. Key Motivators of stakeholder Groups.....60
- 3.6.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups.....61
- 4. European Stakeholder, Projects and Platforms Mapping64
 - 4.1. European Stakeholder Mapping64
 - 4.2. European projects mapping and engagement entry points65
 - 4.3. European platforms mapping and engagement entry points4
- 5. Stakeholder engagement.....6
 - 5.1. Purpose and scope6
 - 5.2. Roles and responsibilities6
 - 5.3. Initial engagement plan7
 - 5.3.1. Methodology7
 - 5.3.2. Engagement of Use Cases and CRNS stakeholders8
 - 5.3.2.1. Next steps for the engagement plan for UCs and CRNs8
 - 5.3.3. Engagement levels for further actors9
 - 5.3.3.1. Engagement levels for European stakeholders9
 - 5.3.4. Engagement levels for European Projects11
 - 5.4. Process to develop PRECIOUS engagement plans12
- 6. Next Steps to advance the PRECIOUS mission.....13
- 7. References14
- Annex 115
 - Stakeholder Mapping Template.....15

List of Tables

Table 1: International and European Stakeholders.....64
 Table 2: Mapping of European projects and engagement entry points.....65
 Table 3: Mapping of European platforms and engagement entry points.....4
 Table 4: The framework used to identify the appropriate level of engagement, adapted from the IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation.....7
 Table 5: Engagement levels for European stakeholders.....9
 Table 6: Engagement levels for European projects.....11
 Table 7: Template to plan stakeholder engagement.....12

List of Figures

Figure 1: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Greece.....15
 Figure 2: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Greece16
 Figure 3: Average Interest and Influence by Geographic Scope, Greece17
 Figure 4: Interest-Influence Matrix, Greece17
 Figure 5: Relations to Stakeholders, Greece18
 Figure 6: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Greece.....19
 Figure 7: Relations to Stakeholders by Geographic Scope, Greece19
 Figure 8: Key Motivators, Greece20
 Figure 9: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Greece21
 Figure 10: Key Motivators by FLWPR Engagement Level, Greece.....21
 Figure 11: Key Barriers, Greece.....22
 Figure 12: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Greece22
 Figure 13: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Spain.....24
 Figure 14: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Spain.....25
 Figure 15: Average Interest and Influence by Geographic Scope, Spain.....26
 Figure 16: Interest-Influence Matrix, Spain27
 Figure 17: Food Waste Contribution and Influence Rating, Spain28
 Figure 18: FLWPR Engagement and Influence Rating, Spain.....28
 Figure 19: Relations to Stakeholders, Spain.....29
 Figure 20: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Spain.....30
 Figure 21: Relations to Stakeholders by Geographic Scope, Spain30
 Figure 22: Key Motivators, Spain31
 Figure 23: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Spain.....32
 Figure 24: Key Motivators by FLWPR Engagement Level, Spain.....32
 Figure 25: Key Barriers, Spain.....33
 Figure 26: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Spain34
 Figure 27: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Hungary35
 Figure 28: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Hungary.....36
 Figure 29: Interest-Influence Matrix, Hungary37
 Figure 30: Food Waste Contribution and Influence Rating, Hungary38
 Figure 31: FLWPR Engagement and Influence Rating, Hungary38
 Figure 32: Relations to Stakeholders, Hungary.....39
 Figure 33: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Hungary40
 Figure 34: Relations to Stakeholders by Geographic Scope, Hungary40
 Figure 35: Key Motivators, Hungary42
 Figure 36: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Hungary.....42
 Figure 37: Key Motivators by FLWPR Engagement Level, Hungary43

Figure 38: Key Barriers, Hungary44

Figure 39: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Hungary44

Figure 40: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Lithuania.....45

Figure 41: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Lithuania47

Figure 42: Average Interest and Influence by Geographic Scope, Lithuania47

Figure 43: Interest-Influence Matrix, Lithuania48

Figure 44: Food Waste Contribution and Influence Rating, Lithuania48

Figure 45: FLWPR Engagement and Influence Rating, Lithuania49

Figure 46: Relations to Stakeholders, Lithuania50

Figure 47: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Lithuania.....50

Figure 48: Key Motivators, Lithuania51

Figure 49: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Lithuania52

Figure 50: Key Motivators by FLWPR Engagement Level, Lithuania.....52

Figure 51: Key Barriers, Lithuania53

Figure 52: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Lithuania54

Figure 53: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Poland.....55

Figure 54: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Poland.....56

Figure 55: Average Interest and Influence by Geographic Scope, Poland.....57

Figure 56: Interest-Influence Matrix, Poland57

Figure 57: FLWPR Engagement and Influence Rating, Poland.....58

Figure 58: Relations to Stakeholders, Poland.....59

Figure 59: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Poland.....59

Figure 60: Relations to Stakeholders by Geographic Scope, Poland60

Figure 61: Key Motivators, Poland61

Figure 62: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Poland.....61

Figure 63: Key Barriers, Poland62

Figure 64: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Poland63

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Meaning
CoP	Community of Practice
CRN	Co-Creation and Replication Node
EU	European Union
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FLWPR	Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Reduction
FSC	Food Supply Chain
PIC Network	Plant InterCluster Network
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Project Overview

If food loss and waste (FLW) were a country, it would be the third leading cause of greenhouse gas emissions. FLW also burdens waste management systems and exacerbates food insecurity, contributing significantly to the three global crises of climate change, nature and biodiversity loss, and pollution and waste.

PRECIOUS, a transdisciplinary alliance of 18 entities from 11 EU countries, believes that reliable data on the environmental impacts of FLW is crucial for accelerating EU progress towards climate targets and reducing environmental impacts (including biodiversity) across the food supply chain. The project's collective understanding is that the challenge goes beyond measuring the amount of food saved or CO₂ emissions. When food is wasted, valuable and limited resources such as water, land use, and energy are lost, therefore depleting the planet's natural resources. It is critical to broaden our understanding of the issue to transform the food system and raise public awareness that motivates change.

PRECIOUS aims to contribute to the transformation of food systems by addressing existing data gaps and developing a unified and openly accessible evaluation framework to quantify the economic, environmental, and social impacts of strategies to reduce FLW, considering potential rebound effects.

The project will engage stakeholders from 2 Use Cases (Spain and Greece) and 3 Co-creation and Replication Nodes (Poland, Lithuania, Hungary) to address systemic causes across geographical boundaries. The project aims to induce a fundamental change in attitudes and behaviours towards food consumption and disposal through collaborative efforts and innovative methods, fostering a more just and sustainable EU food system.

1.2. Deliverable Summary

Stakeholder engagement is a key component of the PRECIOUS approach. This deliverable D6.1 includes a stakeholder mapping of the use cases and the co-creation and replication nodes, as well as relevant European stakeholders, EU projects, and EU platforms. Based on this, it further puts forward an initial engagement plan, detailing entry points for involvement of external actors for feedback, co-creation as well as dissemination and replication of PRECIOUS activities and results.

The **stakeholder mapping** is aimed at reviewing existing actors within the Use Cases (UCs) and Co-Creation Nodes (CRN) locations, as well as on the European level in order to support

- a) The development of effective Communities of Practice (CoP) within the UC locations,
- b) Effective stakeholder engagement formats in the CRNs,
- c) Engagement of European actors such as associations, platforms and projects.

The stakeholder mapping is aimed at understanding stakeholder interrelations and dependencies within the CRN and CoP locations. Their analysis covers all food supply chain stages. By analysing stakeholder composition, positions in the food supply chain, their interests and influence, challenges and motivations, this exercise informs the PRECIOUS engagement plan to mitigate risks and to enable effective stakeholder engagement. The CSCP designed the process to ensure consistency and comparability, while local partners conducted assessments using a semi-open template, iteratively refined through their feedback. Stakeholders were then evaluated using both the quantitative and qualitative assessments provided by local project partners. In addition to location-specific mappings, an EU-level stakeholder mapping was conducted to identify key projects under the Horizon funding scheme, platforms, and organizations for knowledge exchange and collaboration. These were mapped according to thematic relevance. This comprehensive mapping lays the groundwork for a targeted engagement plan.

The initial **engagement plan** details the entry points to engage stakeholder groups across the Use Cases and Co-Creation Nodes, as well as the European stakeholders, projects and platforms. For each of these stakeholder groups, actions are defined across different engagement intensity levels to suggest concrete engagement opportunities and formats for each level. Discussion points are highlighted for partners' further consideration to inform a further, joint refinement of this initial engagement plan to detail the engagement, process and discussion priorities within the course of the PRECIOUS project.

How to read this document

This document consists of two main parts: The stakeholder mapping and analysis (part 1, beginning with Chapter 3), and the initial engagement plan (part 2, beginning with Chapter 5). The stakeholder mapping and analysis is structured by each location of the CoPs and the CRNs, followed by the EU level mapping of stakeholders, projects and platforms.

For a quick read, we recommend selecting your location of interest and focus on the indicated **Engagement Entry Points**. The European Stakeholder Mapping includes separate sections on European stakeholders, projects and platforms. Thereafter, section 5 onwards describes the approach for stakeholder engagement, while 5.3. details the initial engagement plans and 5.4. describes the process to further develop the engagement plans.

2. Introduction

Stakeholder engagement is a cornerstone of PRECIOUS. This document presents the Stakeholder Mapping and Initial Engagement Plan for PRECIOUS, an EU-funded initiative dedicated to reducing food waste through innovative solutions. It aims to support project partners and stakeholders in understanding the key actors involved, their interests, and the initial plan for engagement. PRECIOUS aims to contribute to the transformation of food systems by addressing existing data gaps and developing a unified and openly accessible evaluation framework to quantify the economic, environmental, and social impacts of strategies to reduce food loss and waste (FLW), while considering potential rebound effects.

2.1. Planned PRECIOUS Multi-Stakeholder Engagement Formats: CoPs and CRNs

PRECIOUS is developing a range of technical solutions, integrated assessment models and other tools as part of the PRECIOUS Open Data tool suite with the aim to quantify the economic, environmental, and social impacts of Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Reduction (FLWPR) strategies across the entire FSC, considering potential rebound effects.

To verify the methodologies, tools, and assessments with real-world data, two **Use Cases (UCs)** are engaged in the project that will be testing developed solutions:

- In Greece, the Use Case consists of two companies, namely RIZES GREEK DELICATESSEN focusing on vegetable products and FONTE DI VITA within the fruit supply chain.
- In Spain, the meat processing company VEGALSA is engaged.

The technical implementation is facilitated by WP3 – Use Cases Implementation, while the engagement of stakeholders through Communities of Practice is supported in WP6 – Multi-Actor Approach: Co-creation & Replication activities.

A key element of the PRECIOUS approach is to establish **Communities of Practice (CoP)** in each of the Use Case locations. A CoP is a group of individuals with shared interests, challenges, or a common profession who come together to exchange knowledge, collaborate, and learn collectively to improve their skills and expertise in a particular field. The aim of the CoPs in PRECIOUS is to enable exchange of best practices as well as ensure long-term key stakeholder and (end-users) activation across each UC's region to discuss and provide feedback to WP3, and other PRECIOUS tasks, e.g. Task 1.4, Task 5.1, and Task 5.3. The CoPs can be an opportunity to find common approaches and solutions to implement developed FLWPR measures and further reduce FLW in the supply chain.

In addition, **Co-Creation and Replication Nodes (CRNs)** organised by the local partners in Poland, Lithuania and Hungary, will play a key role in both co-creation efforts and the replication of proposed solutions. CRNs will contribute insights from various actors within the food supply chain (FSC) and actively participate in several project tasks. Their involvement will ensure the dissemination of PRECIOUS outcomes beyond the initial Use Cases. The CRNs will be instrumental in replication activities, encouraging early adoption of project solutions in their locations and fostering long-term sustainability beyond the project's duration.

To support effective engagement of stakeholder in the Use Case and CRNs locations, the stakeholder mapping and analysis was carried out for each location.

2.2. Objective of PRECIOUS Stakeholder Mapping

The primary objective of this document is to identify and suggest engagement approaches for stakeholders who are critical to the success of PRECIOUS. The stakeholder mapping is aimed at understanding stakeholder interrelations and dependencies within the CoP and CRN locations. By analysing stakeholder composition, positions in the food supply chain, their interests and influence, challenges and motivations, this exercise informs the engagement plan to mitigate risks and to enable effective stakeholder engagement. Stakeholders were evaluated using both quantitative and qualitative assessments provided by local project partners. The CSCP designed the process to ensure consistency and comparability, while local partners conducted assessments using a semi-open template (provided in Annex 1), iteratively refined through their feedback. In addition to location-specific mappings, an EU-level stakeholder mapping was conducted to identify key projects, platforms, and organizations for knowledge exchange and collaboration. These were mapped according to thematic relevance and sister projects under the Horizon funding scheme are also included. This comprehensive mapping lays the groundwork for a targeted engagement plan, ensuring key actors are effectively involved in collaborative efforts to reduce food loss and waste.

2.3. Suggested PRECIOUS Initial Engagement Plan

The initial engagement plan details the entry points to engage stakeholder groups across the Use Cases and Co-Creation Nodes, as well as the European stakeholders, projects and platforms. For each of these stakeholder groups, initial entry points for engaging identified stakeholders are detailed. Actions are defined across different engagement intensity levels, to suggest concrete engagement opportunities and formats for each level, and discussion points are highlighted for partners' further consideration.

This document sets the foundation for stakeholder engagement throughout the project. It will be continuously refined based on stakeholder interactions, feedback, and emerging project needs. Future iterations will build on this initial plan, ensuring a dynamic and responsive approach to stakeholder involvement. The conclusions summarize key insights from the engagement process and outline next steps to enhance collaboration and impact. This initial engagement plan will be further refined to detail the engagement, process and discussion priorities in the CoP governance framework (D6.2). In addition, the Replication Protocol under WP6 will detail the approach for the CRNs, while this deliverable together with D7.9 – Plan for Exploitation, dissemination and communication will provide the basis to elaborate a joint work plan for European projects and the engagement of EU platforms.

3. Stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder mapping is an essential component of PRECIOUS’ stakeholder engagement approach. It enhances the understanding of stakeholder interrelations and interdependencies within the CoPs – linked to the Use Cases – and the CRNs locations and directly contributes to the engagement plan. By analysing the composition of stakeholder groups, their position within the food supply chain, and their interests and challenges, the engagement approach can be refined to mitigate risks and enhance effectiveness in achieving both the project’s objectives and stakeholder needs.

The following sections outline the stakeholder analysis methodology, and present the country-specific findings. Along with the findings, recommendations for the engagement approach are highlighted in the form of Engagement Decision Points and Engagement Entry Points.

Engagement Decision Points:

- Engagement Decision Points highlight **challenges or aspects that require conscious consideration**. These aspects will be jointly explored with the local partners in view of the project’s objectives and the local stakeholders’ interests, **to co-create targeted and effective stakeholder engagement** in the PRECIOUS project.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Engagement Entry Points highlight **opportunities to connect** with stakeholders. These entry points can serve as a base for further engagement steps in the PRECIOUS project.

3.1. Stakeholder analysis methodology

As part of the PRECIOUS project on FLWPR, a stakeholder mapping exercise was conducted to identify key actors across the food supply chain and assess their roles, interests, and influence for each of the two use cases and three CRNs. This process followed the general stakeholder mapping approach outlined by Enserink et al. (2022).

- Stakeholders were evaluated based on their level of **interest** and **influence** in FLWPR, using both a numerical scale (ranging from 1 to 10) and qualitative assessments provided by the local project partners.
- Additionally, **their stance** toward the project’s objectives on FLWPR was considered, alongside a qualitative analysis of their **interests, motivators, challenges, and needs**.

The mapping was conducted through a structured yet flexible methodology. The general process was designed by the CSCP with the goal to have comparable and reliable outcomes. The local project partners, who have built expertise through established networks across the food supply chains in all five locations, were responsible for identifying and assessing stakeholders. A semi-open template was used to ensure consistency across locations while allowing for local variations. The template was initially developed by CSCP and refined through feedback from project partners involved in stakeholder engagement activities. The template is provided in Annex 1.

The analysis covered all major stages of the food supply chain, including primary production, processing and manufacturing, distribution, food services, households, and end-of-life stage. In addition to these linear stages, circular food value chain sub-stages were considered, including reprocessing and redistribution. Cross-stage stakeholders such as political and research organizations were considered as well, due to their critical role in shaping policies and driving innovation in food loss and waste reduction.

In parallel to the 5 stakeholder mapping exercises, specific to the CoP and CRN locations, a stakeholder mapping was conducted on European level. This EU-level mapping had a narrower focus towards identifying projects, platforms, and organizations for a cross-European exchange, facilitating knowledge sharing, mutual learning, and the discussion on best practices.

This stakeholder mapping exercise provides a foundation for a targeted engagement plan within the PRECIOUS project, ensuring that key actors are effectively involved in collaborative efforts to reduce food loss and waste.

3.2. Greek CoP

The Greek CoP, organized by CluBE as a CoP, will implement FLWPR actions in the Fruit & Vegetable Food Supply Chain (FSC). The Greek UC will focus on two businesses of the processing and manufacturing stage: RIZES GREEK DELICATESSEN specializing in vegetable and fruit spreads as well as ready-to-eat meals, and FONTE DI VITA, processing fruit products. Both companies were selected due to their existing commitment to waste minimization and valorisation measures, making them strong examples of sustainable practices in the sector.

The UC already offers a solid foundation for engaging stakeholders, as CluBE plays a central role in engaging stakeholders through cross-stage collaboration, ensuring long-term stakeholder involvement and knowledge exchange. In the context of Western Macedonia's transition from lignite mining to a greener economy, these efforts are particularly relevant to implement sustainable measures. Although there is strong interest in FLWPR, the following challenges may hinder effective actions:

- Fragmented collaboration between key stakeholders, including policy makers, businesses, farmers, NGOs, and consumers.
- Lack of financial incentives and policy support to encourage adopting sustainable food management practices.
- Limited public awareness and deeply rooted cultural habits around food consumption and waste.

These factors influence the approach to stakeholder engagement and the development of effective FLWPR strategies in the region. They were carefully considered in the analysis of the stakeholder mapping results.

In an additional survey on engagement formats within the PRECIOUS consortium (Task 6.5), further engagement needs were identified. Based on these, the following engagement decision points inform the CoP's engagement approach in addition to the points identified in the stakeholder mapping exercise:

Engagement Decision Points:

- In an effort to contribute to the educational campaigns related to FLWPR (Task 7.5), suitable educational centres will need to be identified and the material will need to be tailored to the target audience. It should be discussed to what extent the CoPs can support or facilitate this process.
- The alignment of the UC activities (WP3) and the CoP (WP6) will further need to be developed, in order to use synergies between both formats.

3.2.1. Stakeholder Composition

In the Greek stakeholder mapping, a total of 73 stakeholders were considered across 8 distinct food supply chain (FSC) stages. See Figure 1: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Greece for more details.

- Most stakeholders were part of the **processing and manufacturing** stage (35), which **aligns with the UC actors**, which are centred around this stage as well.
- The second most relevant group is the “other” stage (18), which includes many **cross-stage and non-food actors**, such as political actors, the research sector and technology providers.
- A total of 8 stakeholders of the **packaging stage** were included.
- The **distribution stage** counts most stakeholders (7). Retail counts 3, another 3 are active in the redistribution sub-stage, and 1 in other forms of distribution. A total of 4 stakeholders were mapped in the primary production sector.

Engagement Decision Points:

- The **food services stage** and the **household stage** are currently not represented in the stakeholder mapping in the Greece CoP. To tackle especially the challenge of **limited public awareness** and **deeply rooted cultural habits** around food consumption, it may be worth integrating stakeholders from this sector.
- At the moment, the household sector has not been included. Looking at the contextual challenges of a traditional food culture, the question arises whether involving the household sector in the CoP might be beneficial? **Whether and how to include household-stage stakeholders** will need to be discussed in collaboration with the Task 1.4 leads.
- In view of the stakeholder engagement under Work Package (WP) 5 and Task 1.4, one next step should be to **discuss with the task leads** whether the current stakeholder composition needs to be expanded.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The high stakeholder count in the processing and manufacturing stage can provide a good basis for the stakeholder engagement, if the CoP’s scope is set accordingly.

Count of Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage

Figure 1: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Greece

3.2.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups

Among the mapped stakeholders, there is already a generally **high interest** to reduce food loss and waste. Further, the mapped stakeholders were considered **highly influential** to achieve progress in food loss and waste prevention. This can be seen across Figure 2 to Figure 4.

- The overall high rankings can be a result of a **selection bias**, since the local partner focused especially on those actors that already have a higher interest in FLWPR.
- Still, there are nuanced differences in the stakeholder groups. The cross-stage and less defined group of “other” stakeholders had significantly lower interest and influence ratings.
- The Interest-Influence Matrix (Figure 4) demonstrates a lot of the nuances in differences among the mapped stakeholders. For instance, the green-filled shapes indicate that there is a considerable set of stakeholders with a cross-stage dependence score that’s higher than 8.

Engagement Decision Points:

- The current influence and interest ratings seem rather high across all stakeholder categories, which indicates a significant bias, either in the selection or ranking of the stakeholders. As a result, a selection of stakeholders based on the interest and influence rating would likely result in a suboptimal consortium.
- Relying on food waste prevention engagement rankings and categorizations of how the business model is affected by FLWPR will yield more reliable insights on which stakeholders should be engaged.

Figure 2: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Greece

Figure 3: Average Interest and Influence by Geographic Scope, Greece

Figure 4: Interest-Influence Matrix, Greece

3.2.3. Relations to Mapped Stakeholders

Figure 5 to Figure 7 highlight the existing relationship of the Greek local partners to different stakeholder groups.

Relations to mapped stakeholders:

1. The local partner has a working relationship to more than 40% of mapped stakeholders (Figure 5).
2. This share differs considerably by FSC stage, with **close ties to the stages of primary production, end-of-life**, and other, and weaker connections to the distribution stage (Figure 6).
3. Looking at the stakeholders by their scope of operations, there are **strong ties to European, International, and regional** stakeholders, with weaker ties to national and local stakeholders (Figure 7).

Engagement Decision Points:

1. To drive regional change towards reduced food loss and waste, intensifying the connection to regional and local stakeholders will prove valuable. Designing the engagement approach to cater to these two groups will be essential.

Engagement Entry Points:

2. Making use of the good international and European relations can be useful for the European objectives of the PRECIOUS project and should therefore be built upon.
3. Building on existing relations of the local host can provide an entry point for the recruitment of further stakeholders with similar interests.

Stakeholder Relationship Type

Figure 5: Relations to Stakeholders, Greece

Figure 6: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Greece

Figure 7: Relations to Stakeholders by Geographic Scope, Greece

3.2.4. Key Motivators of Stakeholder Groups

Looking at the key motivators is crucial to develop the most compelling arguments to engage stakeholders in the CoPs.

Key Motivators:

- As highlighted in Figure 8, arguments regarding **knowledge exchange and cross-stage learning** seem to be particularly compelling.
- Further, the aspect of **corporate social responsibility** was mentioned as a key motivator.
- **Financial benefits** can be potential motivators as well, with increased economic efficiency thanks to FLWPR as a driver for efficiency.
- As highlighted by Figure 9, the **motivators can vary considerably by sector**. Depending on the sector of a stakeholder, using different arguments to convince them to participate in the CoP will be more effective.

- In addition, as highlighted by Figure 10, those stakeholders who are already actively reducing FLW in their operations have a different set of motivators compared to those with a lower current FLW engagement.

Engagement Decision Points:

- It will be relevant to **decide early on which aspects the CoP wants to focus on**. The motivators and barriers can provide support in aligning the CoP’s scope with the interests of the stakeholders and create the right engagement incentives.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Using the **cross-stage learning and exchange, corporate social responsibility, and financial benefits as main arguments** will be most convincing for stakeholders to participate in the CoP.
- Simultaneously, different arguments should be put to the foreground in communication, **depending on the stakeholder’s FSC stage and current FLWPR engagement**.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder’s local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Stakeholder Motivators

Figure 8: Key Motivators, Greece

Figure 9: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Greece

Figure 10: Key Motivators by FLWPR Engagement Level, Greece

3.2.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups

Along with the key motivators, setting up the CoP to reduce barriers for FLWPR for the stakeholders can also serve as a compelling argument to participate in the project’s activities.

Key Barriers:

- Two barriers stand out as the most prevalent ones. Almost half of the stakeholders mapped in Greece see the **lack of financial resources** as a challenge to implement measures for FLW prevention and reduction. Another major barrier for action is the **lack of knowledge** about FLWPR actions (Figure 11: Key Barriers, Greece).
- Depending on the current engagement of the stakeholder regarding FLWPR, different barriers are more prominent. Whereas engaged actors tend to see **financial aspects** as a greater barrier, less engaged stakeholders seem to be concerned with **bureaucratic challenges** and a **lack of knowledge** (Figure 12).

Engagement Decision Points:

- It will be relevant to **decide early on which aspects the Greek CoP wants to focus on**. The motivators and barriers can provide support in aligning the CoP’s scope with the interests of the stakeholders.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Designing the stakeholder engagement to **address the financial concerns** and make a compelling argument for the increased economic efficiency of reduced FLW will encourage more stakeholders to join the Greek CoP.
- Highlighting the CoP’s ability to enable **cross-stage knowledge exchange** will be a great opportunity to engage more stakeholders.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder’s local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Key Barriers for Stakeholders

Figure 11: Key Barriers, Greece

Key Barriers at Different Engagement Levels

The numbers in the circle represent the share.

Figure 12: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Greece

3.3. Spanish CoP

The Use Case (UC) in the Northwest of Spain, focuses on the Food Supply Chain (FSC) of the Spanish meat supplier VEGALSA. The explicit focus on FLWPR strategies in the meat industry was selected due to the high environmental impact of the meat-based food sector. The Community of Practice (CoP) will be hosted in the same context and will enable to recruit stakeholders beyond the partners in VEGALSA's FSC for an effective cross-stage collaboration. ASINCAR will steer the process of engaging stakeholders and replicating best practices with stakeholders in the region.

The UC already provides a good basis for the engagement of stakeholders. The existing relations of VEGALSA and ASINCAR with businesses across the different FSC served as an entry point to the stakeholder analysis and will aid the recruitment of stakeholders.

While generally there is a shared interest in reduction and prevention of FLW, the **following challenges** may complicate effective actions:

- decentralized supply chains
- cultural attitudes toward food consumption
- limited resources for implementing change complicate effective actions.

Other, more peripheral regional challenges include:

- an ageing population
- deeply-rooted food traditions

These challenges may complicate the effectiveness and implementation of consumer-facing FLWPR actions. They were taken into account for the reflection of the stakeholder mapping results in the engagement decision and entry points.

In an additional survey on engagement formats within the PRECIOUS consortium (Task 6.5), additional engagement needs were identified. Based on these, the following engagement decision points inform the CoP's engagement approach in addition to the points identified in the stakeholder mapping exercise:

Engagement Decision Points:

- In an effort to contribute to the educational campaigns related to FLWPR (Task 7.5), suitable educational centres will need to be identified and the material will need to be tailored to the target audience. It should be discussed to what extent the CoPs can support or facilitate this process.
- Further, in an effort to contribute to the communication of actions and results under Task 3.3, it will be helpful to engage further stakeholders along the FSC to replicate and increase the scope of the UC. Whether and how the CoP can support this objective should be discussed by UC leads, task leads, and potentially the CoP participants.

3.3.1. Stakeholder Composition

For the Spanish stakeholder mapping, the local partners ASINCAR collected information on a total of 65 stakeholders. Their mapping reveals the following key observations:

Food Supply Chain Perspective:

- Spanish CoP stakeholders were mapped along the whole food supply chain, **except for the household’s** sector.
- Most stakeholders are represented in the **processing and manufacturing stage (23) and the distribution stage** (retail 2, wholesale 1, redistribution 11).
- In the logic of the UC’s focus topic “meat”, most producing or processing actors deal with **meat** products (10). However, the processing stage also includes businesses with a **non-meat focus**, such as fish processors (2), manufacturers of beverages (3), manufacturers of dairy products (2), and others (7).
- The **redistribution stage is very well represented** with 10 food banks (non-religious and religious), and a food sharing app provider (1).

Count of Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage

Figure 13: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Spain

Engagement Decision Points:

- At the moment, the household sector has not been included. Looking at the contextual challenges of a traditional food culture, the question arises whether involving the household sector in the CoP might be beneficial? **Whether and how to include household-stage stakeholders** can be discussed in collaboration with the Task 1.4 leads.
- In view of the stakeholder engagement under WP5 and Task 1.4, one next step should be to **discuss with the task leads** whether the current stakeholder composition needs to be expanded.
- Which stakeholders to involve will depend on the CoP’s scope, which the local host will have to determine in collaboration with project partners, project objectives, and a view on the needs of the mapped stakeholders.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The current focus on stakeholders of the processing and manufacturing stage provides a potential entry point for the recruitment, if the CoP’s scope is decided on respectively.

3.3.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups

Impact, Interest and Cross-stage Dependence rating Across Supply Chain Stages:

- Stakeholders in the **packaging, retail, and restaurant sectors** showed the **highest average interest** in addressing food loss and waste.

- **Greatest influence** is seen in the **distribution stage**, with retail stakeholders demonstrating the highest interest, followed by those in wholesale and redistribution.
- Interestingly, local partners’ assessment revealed that **more influential stakeholders also exhibited higher cross-stage dependence**—a finding that may seem counterintuitive at first. It could be explained by a relative dependence of the distribution sector on the consumers. It may also be explained by the redistribution actors, who indeed can have a great impact on the reduction of FLW, however they depend on the collaboration with actors of other stages.

Engagement Decision Points:

- The cross-stage dependence of impactful stakeholders could be leveraged as an effective motivator for the engagement.

Stakeholder Metric ■ Average Cross-stage Dependence ■ Average Influence ■ Average Interest

Influence indicates a stakeholder’s relevance in order to achieve meaningful food loss and waste reduction. Interest indicates the stakeholder’s interest to participate in food loss and waste reduction actions. A high cross-stage dependence indicates a limited ability of a stakeholder to reduce food loss and waste independently of other stage’s actors. 1. Primary Production, 2.1 Processing and Manufacturing, 2.3 Packaging, 3.1 Retail, 3.2 Wholesale, 3.3 Redistribution (food banks, apps, food sharing), 4. Restaurants and food services, 6.1 Non-Food: End of Life (Disposal, Waste, Composting, Energy), Other (non-food, political, research, and uncategorised)

Figure 14: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Spain

Geographic scope, Spain:

- The **41 local and regional stakeholders** (9 local + 32 regional) are seen to have **direct influence** over their operations, which would enable immediate action to reduce food loss and waste.
- However, their **impact remains decentralized**, as their market share is often too small to drive systemic change in the broader food supply chain.
- The **24 stakeholders with a broader reach** (12 national + 7 European + 5 international) may exert a **more abstract but potentially stronger influence**, shaping food supply trends on a larger scale.

Funded by the European Union

Influence indicates a stakeholder's relevance in order to achieve meaningful food loss and waste reduction. Interest indicates the stakeholder's interest to participate in food loss and waste reduction actions. The geographic scope indicates the scale of the stakeholder's operational focus.

Figure 15: Average Interest and Influence by Geographic Scope, Spain

The characteristics described above can be illustrated using an influence-interest matrix. Below, in addition to highlighting the **interest and influence of mapped stakeholders for FLWPR**, it also indicates the **geographic scope and cross-stage dependence** (Figure 16).

- The distribution shows that the local partners focused their stakeholder identification on those stakeholders that are already potentially more interested and influential, leading to a bias for stakeholders in the “manage closely” quadrant.
- There is a **high level of heterogeneity** of stakeholders in the high influence upper half, both regarding the stakeholder’s scope and their cross-stage dependence.
- The lower influence stakeholders are mostly regional stakeholders with less cross-stage dependence.

Engagement Decision Points:

- Focusing on the stakeholders in the “manage closely” quadrant already provides a diverse set of stakeholders. At the same time, some of the more influential stakeholders and cross-stage dependent stakeholders fall into the “keep satisfied” quadrant. While generally the recommendation is to focus on the stakeholders in the “manage closely” quadrant, it can be discussed whether some of the stakeholders of the “keep satisfied” quadrant should be included as well.
- It may be worth including cross-stage dependent stakeholders from other quadrants.

Figure 16: Interest-Influence Matrix, Spain

FLW Contribution and FLWPR Engagement:

- Figure 17 showcases the food waste contribution, segmented by the influence rating of stakeholders. Each level on the Y-axis represents a different relation of the stakeholder’s operations to food loss and waste. For instance, level 1 hosts stakeholder’s whose business model contributes to FLW as a loss of their operations – this might for instance be the case for food suppliers or producers. Level 4 on the other hand portrays stakeholders’ whose operations actively reduce food loss and waste – such as food banks and social kitchens. By segmenting each level by influence ratings on the X-axis, it is possible to assess which kind of food waste contribution are associated with a higher influence over FLW.
- As highlighted by Figure 17, the influence rating is distributed relatively evenly across different kinds of FLW contribution. **Across all business operations**, from “actively contributing to food waste as a loss of the business model” to “actively reducing food loss and waste through the operations” **relevant stakeholders** have been identified.
- Figure 18 shows stakeholders’ current engagement towards FLWPR, segmented by the influence rating of stakeholders. Each level on the Y-axis represents a different level of FLWPR engagement. The levels reach from 1, “food waste is not important to them and they do not act to reduce it”, to 7, “Food waste is a central issue to them and their organization actively fights it”. By segmenting each level by influence ratings on the X-axis, it is possible to assess which current FLWPR engagement corresponds to different levels of influence over FLW.
- Similarly, as highlighted by Figure 18, the influence of stakeholders is also distributed across different levels of current engagement. What stands out is that the **majority of stakeholders is already aware** of the relevance of FLW, although many stakeholders are **not taking considerable actions** at the moment.

Figure 17: Food Waste Contribution and Influence Rating, Spain

Figure 18: FLWPR Engagement and Influence Rating, Spain

3.3.3. Relations to Mapped Stakeholders

A majority of the mapped stakeholders are already in a working relationship with the local host.

Relations to mapped stakeholders:

- Of 65 mapped stakeholders, **53** were already in a **direct relationship** with the local host, which will help the recruitment process (Figure 19).
- Still, there are **differences across the supply chain** stages. While there are good ties to the stages of primary production, processing and manufacturing, redistribution, end-of-life, and other, the ties to the other stages, such as households and wholesalers, are less well established.
- When looking at the geographical scope of stakeholders, it becomes apparent that there are **well-established ties across all levels**, with potential to increase relations to national stakeholders.

Engagement Decision Points:

- Simultaneously, by clearly **defining the scope of the CoP**, it will be easier to select which stakeholders to recruit in regards of supply chain stages and geographical scope.

Engagement Entry Points:

- **Building on the well-established ties** to various stakeholders is an opportunity to ease the recruitment process for the CoP.

Stakeholder Relationship Type

Figure 19: Relations to Stakeholders, Spain

Figure 20: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Spain

Figure 21: Relations to Stakeholders by Geographic Scope, Spain

3.3.4. Key Motivators of Stakeholder Groups

The key motivators mapped in the Spanish case will enable to design compelling arguments for the recruitment of stakeholders:

- Overall, for a majority of stakeholders “None of the above” was the most-reported answer in the stakeholder mapping template, as seen in Figure 22. In these cases, the following aspects were listed by the local partner:
 - 10 actors were engaged in redistribution activities and are therefore **motivated to reduce FLW intrinsically** as a result of their business philosophy.
 - In 5 instances, the stakeholders were engaged in either developing new **technologies, or advocating** for food safety and food waste reduction on European level, so their motivation

was more to use the platform to **learn about challenges**, which would then inform their strategies.

- In 3 instances, the stakeholders used **animal by-products or surplus products** as their main input. In this case, their motivation to participate is also intrinsically found in their businesses’ operations.
- Of the pre-defined answers, the most common responses were focused on **cross-stage learning and knowledge exchange**, followed by reduced (financial) losses (Figure 22).
- Generally, it can be seen that the share of **key motivators in Spain varies by supply chain stage**. The differences are smaller when looking at the FLWPR engagement levels.

Engagement Decision Points:

- When defining the scope of the CoP, the motivators, barriers, and project objectives should be taken into consideration.
- It is to be discussed which PRECIOUS technological solutions could be of interest to the Spanish stakeholders in view of the motivators and challenges.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Tailoring the **arguments towards the specific key motivators of each supply chain stage** will be helpful to engage stakeholders. The strategy can be similar for both, less and more engaged actors.
- PRECIOUS-related redistribution content could be tested particularly well in Spain.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder’s local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Stakeholder Motivators

Figure 22: Key Motivators, Spain

Key Motivators by Food Supply Chain Stage

Figure 23: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Spain

Key Motivators at Different Engagement Levels

Figure 24: Key Motivators by FLWPR Engagement Level, Spain

3.3.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups

Along with the key motivators, the key **barriers** provide an insight into how to engage the Spanish stakeholders by effectively addressing their challenges in the CoP:

- Remarkable was that **none of the pre-defined answers** of the semi-open survey were suitable in 22 cases. In these cases, it was difficult to identify barriers in the first place. This was particularly the case for food banks and humanitarian organizations, as well as research centres working about food waste (Figure 25).
- For other stakeholders, the key barriers include the risk that food loss and waste practices might be perceived as **uneconomical** in some settings, there might be a lack of **consumer acceptance**, or there

might be difficulties in reducing food waste due to **product standards**. As reported in the mapping, this last aspect is particularly relevant to animal-based products, due to the higher safety standards.

- Overall, the barriers were similar for both high and low FLWPR engagement levels, with product standards playing a more important role for the less engaged stakeholders, whereas behavioural challenges were more relevant to the more engaged stakeholders (Figure 26).

Engagement Decision Points:

- When defining the scope of the CoP, the motivators, barriers, and project objectives should be taken into consideration.
- For food banks, humanitarian organizations, and research centres already working on food waste, it will be necessary to further understand potential barriers for their engagement in PRECIOUS activities.

Engagement Entry Points:

- Designing the stakeholder engagement process to meet the specific barriers of concerns regarding **uneconomical** actions, increasing **consumer acceptance**, and identifying **pathways to reduce FLW while complying with product safety standards** will provide a compelling set of arguments to actors who are not yet intrinsically engaged.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder’s local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Key Barriers for Stakeholders

Figure 25: Key Barriers, Spain

Figure 26: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Spain

3.4. Hungarian CRN

Hungary was selected as a CRN host as for its strategic importance within the European agrifood sector, particularly given its strong agricultural base and the ongoing need for improves FLWPR strategies. While cooperation among agrifood actors, public institutions, and research organizations is developing, it is often limited to international projects or securing national funding. Additionally, retail chains hold significant market power, influencing terms for suppliers, while horizontal collaboration among producers and processors.

The Hungarian Co-creation and Replication Node (CRN), led by INNOMINE DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB (IA), plays a key role In PRECIOS in engaging FSC stakeholders in co-creation activities through cross-stage collaboration. IA already has strong connections with FSC actors and has already provided policy recommendations at local, national and European levels.

Although there is strong interest in FLWPR, the **following challenges** may hinder effective actions:

- Limited horizontal collaboration between agrifood businesses, restricting resource optimization and waste reduction
- Regulatory barriers that complicate food redistribution efforts
- A lack of economic incentives to encourage sustainable food management practices.

These aspects were considered when reflecting on the stakeholder mapping results.

3.4.1. Stakeholder Composition

Food Supply Chain Perspective:

- Most stakeholders are represented in the **processing and manufacturing stage** (9), followed by the **restaurant and food services stage** (8) and **other stakeholders** (5).
- **No actors** have been mapped for **packaging, retail, redistribution, households, and non-food stakeholders**.

Engagement Decision Points:

- At the moment, the **packaging, retail, redistribution, households, and non-food stakeholders** in Hungary are not included. It should be considered whether the current selection of stakeholders will be sufficient in the further stakeholder engagement process. It should be evaluated which stakeholder groups are necessary to achieve improvements on the challenges listed above and in view of the project’s objectives.
- In view of the stakeholder engagement under WP5, one next step should be to **discuss with the task leads** whether the current stakeholder composition needs to be expanded.

Count of Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage

Figure 27: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Hungary

3.4.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups

Impact, Interest and Cross-stage Dependence rating Across Supply Chain Stages:

- Overall, all Hungarian stakeholders seem interested and influential.
- Stakeholders in the primary production sector and other forms of distribution show the highest **average interest** (10.0)
- Stakeholders in the **wholesale sector show the highest average influence** (10.0)
- The processing stakeholder and restaurants and food services stakeholder show a strong correlation between average interest and influence, while the others show a greater divergence between the two factors.

Figure 28: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Hungary

Interest-Influence Stakeholder Matrix

- In Figure 29, all stakeholders are positioned under ‘**manage closely**’, which indicates a **potential selection bias**, meaning the local partner focused their stakeholder identification on those stakeholders that are more influential and have a higher interest. This may have left out other stakeholder groups (see above), which may have lower influence and interest, but are still important to the topic.
- The distribution is very heterogeneous, with no clear distinction between the placement of regional/local/national/European stakeholders.

Engagement Decision Points:

- Given the potential selection bias, it might be worth broadening the scope for the inclusion of further stakeholders in the CRN, depending on how the scope of the CRN will be defined.
- Since the stakeholder’s ranking is comparatively high for both interest and influence across the board, the effectiveness as selection criteria are reduced.

Figure 29: Interest-Influence Matrix, Hungary

Contribution and Engagement

- Figure 30 showcases the food waste contribution, segmented by the influence rating of stakeholders. Each level on the Y-axis represents a different relation of the stakeholder's operations to food loss and waste. For instance, level 1 hosts stakeholder's whose business model contributes to FLW as a loss of their operations – this might for instance be the case for food suppliers or producers. Level 4 on the other hand portrays stakeholders' whose operations actively reduce food loss and waste – such as food banks and social kitchens. By segmenting each level by influence ratings on the X-axis, it is possible to assess which kind of food waste contribution are associated with a higher influence over FLW.
- Figure 30 shows that **most stakeholders in Hungary** contribute to food loss and waste as a **loss of their business model**.
- Figure 31 shows stakeholders' current engagement towards FLWPR, segmented by the influence rating of stakeholders. Each level on the Y-axis represents a different level of FLWPR engagement. The levels reach from 1, "food waste is not important to them and they do not act to reduce it", to 7, "Food waste is a central issue to them and their organization actively fights it". By segmenting each level by influence ratings on the X-axis, it is possible to assess which current FLWPR engagement corresponds to different levels of influence over FLW.
- Simultaneously, Figure 31 shows that the **majority of actors are already somewhat aware of the relevance of FLWPR but could do more within their operations**.

Engagement Decision Points:

- Since most identified stakeholders are contributing to FLW but are somewhat aware and only working on reducing it to a limited extent, the Hungarian CRN could focus on

measures that would help these stakeholders to more successfully apply FLWPR actions.

Figure 30: Food Waste Contribution and Influence Rating, Hungary

Figure 31: FLWPR Engagement and Influence Rating, Hungary

3.4.3. Relations to Stakeholders

Relations to stakeholders

- The local partner does not have close ties to the majority of identified stakeholders at the moment.
- This observation holds across all supply chain stages and the geographical scopes.

Engagement Decision Points:

- As a result of the lacking ties to food supply chain actors, the local host in Hungary will have more **difficulties recruiting stakeholders** for the CRN activities. Especially the lack of relations to the local level might make the testing, replication, and co-creation of FLWPR approaches more difficult.
- **Different strategies should be discussed** to enable the local partner to set up the CRN in a way that allows effective co-creation and replication in Hungary.

Stakeholder Relationship Type

Figure 32: Relations to Stakeholders, Hungary

Figure 33: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Hungary

Figure 34: Relations to Stakeholders by Geographic Scope, Hungary

3.4.4. Key Motivators of Stakeholder Groups

- As highlighted by Figure 35, the strongest motivators in Hungary are benefits for corporate social responsibility (8), followed by reduced financial losses (6).
- For the primary production stage and other forms of distribution, a **platform for knowledge exchange and learning is the dominant motivator**, whereas **reduced financial losses** are named as a motivator among three stakeholder groups – Processing and distribution (44%), Wholesale (100%), and Restaurants and food services (12%). **Benefits for corporate social responsibility** is a motivator for the processing and distribution stage (56%) and the restaurant and food services stage (38%)
- Looking at the different FLWPR engagement levels, it appears that the motivators for currently less engaged actors seem to be less clear, as there was no information provided on more than half of low engagement stakeholders.

Engagement Decision Points:

- As a result of the lacking ties to food supply chain actors, the local host will have more **difficulties recruiting stakeholders** for the CRN activities. Especially the lack of relations to the local level might make the testing, replication, and co-creation of FLWPR approaches more difficult.
- **Discuss with PRECIOUS partners** which offers are available to stakeholders to reduce financial losses and increase benefits to corporate social responsibility.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The motivators can be an entry point to develop a scope or objectives for the CRN.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder's local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Stakeholder Motivators

Figure 35: Key Motivators, Hungary

The numbers in the circle represent the share.

Figure 36: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Hungary

Figure 37: Key Motivators by FLWPR Engagement Level, Hungary

3.4.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups

- The most common barrier in Hungary overall is behavioural challenge (8), followed by technological challenges (4).
- Overall, the barriers are much **more heterogeneously distributed** than the motivators, which many being mentioned for 1 or 2 stakeholders only.
- Among the high engagement, **behavioural challenges** are the most common challenge, whereas among the low engagement, the most common barrier is **technological challenges**, with exception the stakeholders for whom no further barriers were mentioned. **This indicates that more engaged stakeholders should be approached differently than less engaged stakeholders.**

Engagement Decision Points:

- The more heterogenous distribution of key challenges makes it difficult to identify a clear engagement strategy as of now. This means other aspects might be more useful to define a scope for the Hungarian CRN. For instance, basing the CRN’s focus on the projected Use Case learnings and then engaging stakeholders that would be necessary to replicate and adapt actions might be an alternative way forward.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder’s local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Key Barriers for Stakeholders

Figure 38: Key Barriers, Hungary

Key Barriers at Different Engagement Levels

The numbers in the circle represent the share.

Figure 39: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Hungary

3.5. Lithuanian CRN

The Lithuanian Co-Creation and Replication Node is hosted by Agrifood Lithuania. With their expertise in technological innovation and sustainable business models for the agricultural and food sector, they can build upon their existing network of stakeholders to enable cross-stage collaboration. Their strong focus on technological innovation can be an advantage in deploying novel technological solutions for FLWPR. However, challenges may present in effective engagement of actors from the household sector and the primary production.

3.5.1. Stakeholder Composition

The stakeholder composition of the Lithuanian CoP provides an overview of the supply chain stages represented in the stakeholder mapping:

- Lithuanian CoP stakeholders were mapped along the whole food-supply chain, **except for the wholesale and restaurants and food sourcing stages.**
- Most stakeholders are represented in the **primary production stage (10), followed by the processing stage (6) and others (non-food, political, research, uncategorized) (6).**
- The majority of stakeholders operate on a **national scope (22)**, with only 1 European and 3 local stakeholders.

Engagement Decision Points:

- The wholesale and food services sector are not represented in the mapping. Depending on the objectives of the CRN, it may or may not be necessary to include actors of these stages as well.
- In view of the stakeholder engagement under WP5, one next step should be to **discuss with the task leads** whether the current stakeholder composition needs to be expanded.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The current focus on the primary production and processing stages makes effective use of Agrifood Lithuania’s network, as also indicated by the relations Figure 47. Focusing on these stakeholders and building the CRN around their interests can be an entry point.

Count of Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage

Figure 40: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Lithuania

3.5.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups

The following insights on interest and influence of stakeholder groups were derived in the Lithuanian case:

- As demonstrated by Figure 41 and the stakeholder matrix in Figure 43, the mapped stakeholders generally had a high interest in FLWPR. As a result, it can be argued that the local partner conducted the mapping with a targeted view on the most interest stakeholders, leading to a **selection bias**.
- Still, differences can be identified. For instance, household actors, processing and manufacturing, and end-of-life stakeholders were seen as less influential, while **primary producers, redistributors, and other non-food actors were seen as more influential**.
- Looking at the geographical scope, it becomes apparent that the **focus was set on the national level**, with 22 stakeholders, while there were only 3 local and 1 European stakeholder included. Overall, the influence was also seen to be higher with these national stakeholders (Figure 42).
- Figure 44 showcases the food waste contribution, segmented by the influence rating of stakeholders. Each level on the Y-axis represents a different relation of the stakeholder's operations to food loss and waste. By segmenting each level by influence ratings on the X-axis, it is possible to assess which kind of food waste contribution are associated with a higher influence over FLW.
- Looking at FLW contribution, the majority of mapped stakeholders were considered to fall under category 5 (other) (Figure 44). These stakeholders all either have a representative, consulting, or regulative function and thus do not contribute to FLW directly.
- Figure 45 shows stakeholders' current engagement towards FLWPR, segmented by the influence rating of stakeholders. Each level on the Y-axis represents a different level of FLWPR engagement. The levels reach from 1, "food waste is not important to them and they do not act to reduce it", to 7, "Food waste is a central issue to them and their organization actively fights it". By segmenting each level by influence ratings on the X-axis, it is possible to assess which current FLWPR engagement corresponds to different levels of influence over FLW.
- As highlighted by Figure 45, the **majority of identified stakeholders is already actively reducing FLW**. This means that the engagement strategy for the Lithuanian CRN will have to particularly pay attention to the motivators and barriers of those stakeholders that are already active in FLWPR.

Engagement Decision Points:

- It will be necessary to determine early on to what extent the CRN aims to replicate and test activities of the Use Cases. Only by determining this and considering the project's KPIs it will be possible to assess whether or not it will be sufficient to focus on the national stakeholders.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The CRN can focus on national stakeholders with a more indirect contribution on FLWPR. Many of the mapped stakeholders have a representative function for stakeholders in primary production, and processing stages. Designing the CRN to cater to these representative member organizations could allow for large **multiplier effects**.
- Most stakeholders are already aware of the relevance of FLWPR and are somewhat active. The **CRN could therefore be promoted as a tool to support these stakeholders** to support their current engagement with new insights and frameworks, that lead to a higher effectiveness of the efforts.

Figure 41: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Lithuania

Figure 42: Average Interest and Influence by Geographic Scope, Lithuania

Figure 43: Interest-Influence Matrix, Lithuania

Figure 44: Food Waste Contribution and Influence Rating, Lithuania

Figure 45: FLWPR Engagement and Influence Rating, Lithuania

3.5.3. Relations to Stakeholders

The relations to stakeholders can support the engagement in early stages:

- Out of the 26 stakeholders, 14 have a direct relationship, and 12 have only a distant or lacking relationship (Figure 46).
- Generally, the network of the local host is well-equipped to reach out to primarily **national stakeholders** with a root in the primary production stage, the other non-food sector, and processing and manufacturing.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The network of the local partner allows multiple entry points to national stakeholders.

Stakeholder Relationship Type

Figure 46: Relations to Stakeholders, Lithuania

The numbers in the circle represent the share.

Figure 47: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Lithuania

3.5.4. Key Motivators of Supply Groups

The key motivators are a great basis to develop compelling arguments for stakeholder engagement:

- The most common motivators are **learning best practices** (9) and **reduced (financial) losses** (8), followed by the **achievement of policy objectives** (5).
- Looking at the **supply chain stages, there are considerable differences in key motivators**. Taking into account the stakeholder counts in each supply chain stage, the most important stages to **focus on are primary production, processing and manufacturing, and other non-food**. In this case, creating a platform that addresses policy objectives, while providing opportunities for collaboration and mutual learning will be most ideal. To engage stakeholders for this platform, the argument of reducing financial losses can be appealing to primary producers and other non-food stakeholders.
- Considering the **engagement levels, learning best practices** comes out as the strongest motivator for both.

Engagement Decision Points:

- A somewhat coherent set of arguments can be presented for a national collaborative platform on FLWPR. This however requires consideration in view of the project’s KPIs and the scope of the CRN.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder’s local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Stakeholder Motivators

Figure 48: Key Motivators, Lithuania

Key Motivators by Food Supply Chain Stage

Figure 49: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Lithuania

Key Motivators at Different Engagement Levels

Figure 50: Key Motivators by FLWPR Engagement Level, Lithuania

3.5.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups

The key barriers provide relevant information on how stakeholders can be approached effectively:

- Figure 51 highlights four key challenges. **Technological challenges** (11) and lack of **financial resources** (9) are the most relevant ones, followed by **bureaucratic** (2) and **other** (4) challenges. In case of the other motivators, no additional information was provided.
- Looking at the different engagement levels, technological challenges seem relevant for those actors, who are already more engaged in FLWPR, whereas for the less engaged stakeholders financial and other aspects seem more relevant.

Engagement Decision Points:

- The technological challenges could make use of the local host’s expertise in innovative technologies for the agricultural and foods sector. Whether or not this aspect can be a main focus of the CRN depends to some extent on whether the Use Cases will provide new technological solutions.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder’s local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Key Barriers for Stakeholders

Figure 51: Key Barriers, Lithuania

Figure 52: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Lithuania

3.6. Polish CRN

The Polish Co-creation and Replication Node (CRN), led by UNIMOS Alliance (UA), is part of a network collaborating across sectors, with participation in several sustainability driven and FLW related projects. UA already created alliances with a wide range of stakeholders, including agri-food producers (meat, dairy, cereals, fruits and vegetables), logistic experts, processors, and consumers, as well as stakeholders from bioeconomy, packaging, and digital value chains. The collaboration is further strengthened by the involvement of the PIC Network, which consists of 12 EU plant-based clusters.

Through these initiatives, Poland benefits from a well-established foundation for cross-stage collaboration, which is essential for scaling up FLWPR actions. Despite this, challenges remain that hinder the full effectiveness of FLWPR strategies, particularly:

- Limited consumer awareness and behaviour change related to FLW
- Cultural practices and traditional habits
- Lack of clear legal regulations surrounding food donation, which can complicate redistribution efforts
- Insufficient engagement from public-sector actors, which can slow down the adoption of sustainable food management practices.

These challenges need to be addressed for the continued success and scalability of FLWPR in Poland and were considered when considering the results of the stakeholder mapping.

3.6.1. Stakeholder Composition

In the Polish CRN, the stakeholder mapping identified stakeholders of the following supply chain stages:

- Of the **22 stakeholders** mapped in the Polish CRN, 11 are part of the **distribution stage**, with 1 stakeholder of the retail sub-stage, 2 stakeholders in the wholesale sub-stage, and 8 stakeholders from the re-distribution stage.

- 4 stakeholders of the **primary production stage** were included in the mapping, with a focus on scientific and technical support to the primary production stage, and one producer of forest fruits and citrus.
- In the **processing and manufacturing stage**, the stakeholders had different backgrounds in the meat, dairy, and baked goods industry.
- Overall, a majority of actors had a national scope (11), whereas 4 each had a regional and international scope, and 3 had a local scope.

Engagement Decision Points:

- The stakeholder composition could enable the CRN to take **two different routes**. On the one hand, it could focus on FLWPR actions relating to the **distribution stage**, particularly re-distribution. On the other hand, it could focus on the primary production and processing stages, to **test and replicate** the Use Case results in other food sectors.
- Looking at the **local challenges** for FLWPR, another aspect to consider is whether or not to engage more public actors or actors of the **household stage**. Tackling cultural practices and traditional habits, as well as changing the awareness of FLW will require collaboration with household stakeholders. Further, the need for further support by the public sector for FLWPR was highlighted as a challenge, which will require engaging **public stakeholders**.
- In view of the stakeholder engagement under WP5, one next step should be to **discuss with the task leads** whether the current stakeholder composition needs to be expanded.
- Another decision is to be made whether the CRN should focus on national stakeholders, or try to recruit additional regional and local stakeholders should be recruited.

Count of Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage

Figure 53: Stakeholder Composition by Food Supply Chain Stage, Poland

3.6.2. Interest and Influence of Stakeholder Groups

Looking at **interest and influence** of different stakeholder groups, interesting insights can be derived for the Polish CRN:

- When comparing Figure 55 to other cases, it becomes apparent that influence and interest are less correlated. As a result, some actors with a high interest in FLWPR highly depend on stakeholders of other supply chain stages to become active, which can for instance be seen in the reprocessing and food services stages. In other stages, influence and interest are more correlated, enabling these actors to become leading actors for FLWPR.

- As indicated by Figure 56, the local partner has attributed the highest influence on FLW to international actors, perhaps since their decisions can have a large impact across various countries. Simultaneously, local actors were seen as those with the highest interest.
- Looking at the stakeholder matrix (Figure 57), it becomes apparent that the only a part of the mapped stakeholders falls under **the manage closely category** (9). Of the 9 stakeholders under this category, the majority (5) are national stakeholders, with 1 regional and 3 international stakeholders.
- An interesting aspect, which stands out for the Lithuanian stakeholder mapping against the other cases, is the aspect of **FLWPR engagement and influence**. The majority of mapped actors are already considering FLWPR a central issue and actively reduce FLW. As a result, the CRN will have to focus less on activating stakeholders and making them aware of the impacts of FLW.

Engagement Decision Points:

- A decision point for the local partner will be whether or not to focus on the national stakeholders. **Depending on the scope** of the CRN, additional regional or local stakeholders may need to be recruited to facilitate testing and replication.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The influence and interest mapping in the Polish CRN can support the selection of stakeholders by focusing on **the most interested and influential actors for the initial engagement**.

Stakeholder Metric ■ Average Cross-stage Dependence ■ Average Influence ■ Average Interest

Influence indicates a stakeholder's relevance in order to achieve meaningful food loss and waste reduction. Interest indicates the stakeholder's interest to participate in food loss and waste reduction actions. A high cross-stage dependence indicates a limited ability of a stakeholder to reduce food loss and waste independently of other stage's actors. 1. Primary Production, 2.1 Processing and Manufacturing, 2.2 Reprocessing, 3.1 Retail, 3.2 Wholesale, 3.3 Redistribution (food banks, apps, food sharing), 4. Restaurants and food services, 6.1 Non-Food: End of Life (Disposal, Waste, Composting, Energy)

Figure 54: Average Interest, Influence, and Interdependence of Stakeholder Groups, Poland

Funded by the European Union

Influence indicates a stakeholder's relevance in order to achieve meaningful food loss and waste reduction. Interest indicates the stakeholder's interest to participate in food loss and waste reduction actions. The geographic scope indicates the scale of the stakeholder's operational focus.

Figure 55: Average Interest and Influence by Geographic Scope, Poland

Influence indicates a stakeholder's relevance in order to achieve meaningful food loss and waste reduction. Interest indicates the stakeholder's interest to participate in food loss and waste reduction actions. The geographic scope indicates the scale of the stakeholder's operational focus. A high cross-stage dependence indicates a limited ability of a stakeholder to reduce food loss and waste independently of other stage's actors.

Figure 56: Interest-Influence Matrix, Poland

Figure 57: FLWPR Engagement and Influence Rating, Poland

3.6.3. Relations to Stakeholders

The relations to the stakeholders are a starting point for the engagement process. The following findings stand out in the Polish stakeholder mapping:

- The local host already has **direct ties to two fifths** of the stakeholders (Figure 59).
- Looking at the supply chain stages, ties to the primary production stage, food services stage, non-food stage, and retail stage are more established than to other stages.
- Similarly, direct ties focus on the local and regional stakeholders with the potential to increase relations on the national, international, and European scale.

Engagement Decision Points:

- If the local partners opt to focus on the national scope stakeholders, the current connections could be used as a corner stone.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The existing relationships of the local host can provide an entry point towards recruiting more stakeholders with related challenges and interests.

Stakeholder Relationship Type

Figure 58: Relations to Stakeholders, Poland

Figure 59: Relations to Stakeholders by Supply Chain Stage, Poland

Figure 60: Relations to Stakeholders by Geographic Scope, Poland

3.6.4. Key Motivators of stakeholder Groups

Key motivators include in the Lithuanian case are mainly centred **around learning, exchange, and corporate social responsibility**:

- Generally, as highlighted by Figure 62, a lot of key motivators centre around **mutual learning, cross-stage exchange, and best practices** on the one hand, and potential benefits for the **corporate social responsibility on the other hand**.
- While there are little differences by engagement level, it becomes apparent that there are differences across the mapped supply chain stages, with stakeholders of **the processing stage particularly focusing on the corporate social responsibility argument**.

Engagement Decision Points:

- The scope of the CRN can be informed by the stakeholders' key motivators. However, it will be necessary to align with the project's objectives, KPIs, and Use Cases.

Engagement Entry Points:

- To effectively recruit stakeholders, **focusing on the learning and exchange** arguments will be beneficial. When addressing stakeholders in the processing and manufacturing stage, arguments should focus on **benefits to the corporate social responsibility**.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder's local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Stakeholder Motivators

Figure 61: Key Motivators, Poland

Key Motivators by Food Supply Chain Stage

The numbers in the circle represent the share.

Figure 62: Key Motivators by Supply Chain Stage, Poland

3.6.5. Key Barriers of Stakeholder Groups

In addition to the key motivators, the key **barriers** provide an insight into how to engage stakeholders by effectively addressing their challenges in the CoP:

- In the Polish CRN, the key barriers are **distributed very heterogeneously** and key challenges appear across different stakeholder types and supply chain stages.
- Figure 64 provides an overview of the key barriers. The most common challenge were **product standards** (6). These can be grouped with **bureaucratic challenges** (2) and **legal challenges** (1), as all three aspects may create uncertainty or seemingly high knowledge barriers around **accountability and FLWPR**. Three barriers indicate challenges with the demand or awareness of households, as **marketing challenges** (4), **consumer acceptance** (3) and the **lack of demand** (1) were mentioned as key barriers. Lack of **cross-stage collaboration** was pointed out 3 times.
- In the cases (4), where “other” was recorded, the local partner provided the information that food waste is not a key activity of these stakeholders, which in itself constitutes a main barrier.

Engagement Decision Points:

- As a result of the heterogenous distribution of key barriers, a multi-facetted argumentation to engage stakeholders is recommended when approaching stakeholders.

Engagement Entry Points:

- The key barriers allow insights into how to shape the focus of the CRN for more effective engagement. If the Polish CRN focuses on reducing **accountability concerns**, increasing **consumer acceptance** and demand, or enhance **cross-stage collaboration**, the CRN can engage stakeholders more easily.
- The key motivators and key barriers should be taken into account for the **collaboration with WP5**. When WP5 is responsive to these motivators and barriers, it can become a great benefit for the stakeholder’s local, regional, and national FLWPR objectives.

Distribution of Key Barriers for Stakeholders

Figure 63: Key Barriers, Poland

Figure 64: Barriers by FLWPR Engagement, Poland

4. European Stakeholder, Projects and Platforms Mapping

The PRECIOUS project will seek to engage European stakeholders to ensure the robustness of project findings and disseminate project results across the EU. Further, collaboration with related European projects and activities will be sought to build on past knowledge and inform and shape future approaches. In addition, existing European platforms will be leveraged to increase visibility of PRECIOUS and further enhance dissemination and uptake of project activities and results.

The following sections map the European stakeholders, projects and platforms and give recommendations for initial engagement entry points.

4.1. European Stakeholder Mapping

A diverse range of European stakeholders were identified for PRECIOUS, which are important to consider to ensure a comprehensive approach to reducing food waste while achieving a sustainable transition towards net-zero. Additionally, relevant international organisations should also be taken into account. Table 1 illustrates a non-exhaustive list of key stakeholders at EU level, which include relevant EU institutions, policy-makers, consumer groups, industry associations covering food production, processing, retail, and commerce, as well as NGOs and advocacy groups focused on sustainability and waste reduction. The full list of EU stakeholders is accessible for consortium partners on the shared file location. Building on this mapping of European projects, section 5.3.3 outlines engagement formats for different engagement levels.

Table 1: International and European Stakeholders.

	International organisation	EU institution	EU level industry association (food production, processing and services / retail / commerce)	EU level consumer group	EU level NGO/advocacy group
Examples	Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), International Food Waste Coalition (IFWC), World Bank	European Commission, EC Joint Research Centre (JRC), European Economic and Social Committee (EESC), EU Committee of Regions (CoR)	Copa Cogeca, European Fruit and Vegetables Trade Association (EUCOFEL), European Food Banks Federation (FEBA), EUROCOMMERCE, HOTREC,	BEUC – The European Consumer Organisation, European Community of Consumer Co-operatives (EUROCOOP)	Slow Food, Zero Waste, EEB

In addition to the European stakeholders, national-level stakeholders from EU Member States (and potentially from Associated countries) should also be considered in the engagement of PRECIOUS stakeholders, as these can further disseminate PRECIOUS learnings. National stakeholders encompass government bodies, policy makers, waste management and recycling organisations, and networks dedicated to zero waste, food sharing,

and food banks. Additionally, regional and local governments in EU Member States play a crucial role in implementing climate and food-related policies and initiatives tailored to their specific contexts.

Engaging with this wide spectrum of stakeholders is essential for fostering collaboration, shaping effective policies, and driving impactful solutions to food waste across Europe.

4.2. European projects mapping and engagement entry points

To maximize impact and foster synergies, PRECIOUS will actively collaborate with other EU-funded projects, including sister initiatives funded under the FARM2FORK-01-8 call to ensure coordinated efforts in reducing food waste. Further, collaboration with projects under HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-17, focusing on data-driven solutions to enhance industry’s role in inclusive and sustainable food systems, will also be explored. Engagement will also extend to relevant past projects, ensuring that PRECIOUS builds on existing knowledge and avoids duplicating any past efforts. The table below (Table 2) provides an overview of key European projects for potential collaboration, and maps entry points for the engagement. The list of European projects is also available as a ‘living document’ in the shared file location for additions by consortium partners.

Table 2: Mapping of European projects and engagement entry points.

FSC stage	Project	Description	Keywords	Partners involved	Relevant for WP	Engagement entry points
Short supply chains	agroBRIDGES (Inactive)	agroBRIDGES empowers farmers through new business and marketing models based on Short Food Supply Chains (SFSC). The novelty of agroBRIDGES is based on its integrated methodology.	food, agri-food system	Agrifood Lithuania	WP2, WP4, WP6	The agroBRIDGES toolbox and sustainability assessment can inform the PRECIOUS approach.
Primary Production	BREADCRUMB (Active)	BBringing Evidence-based food Chain solutions to prevent and Reduce food waste related to Marketing standards, and deliver climate and circularity co-Benefits. The project will examine five food commodities (fruits & vegetables, meat, eggs, cereals and fish) in 16 multi-actor case studies involving food businesses, research and innovation (R&I) organisations, civil society organisations (CSOs), sectorial associations and consumers across Europe. The aim is to develop a better understanding when, why and to what extent marketing standards lead to food waste.	Food waste, Policy impact, Societal impact, marketing standards	CSCP	WP1, WP3, WP5	BREADCRUMB aims to support the FLWPR by better understanding the impacts of food marketing standards (FMS). The project reviews private and public FMS, collects estimates of FLW related to FMS, models the underlying mechanisms, supports the increase of acceptance of suboptimal foods, and prepares respective policy guidance. PRECIOUS will build upon relevant impact information from BREADCRUMB.
Full food supply chain	Chorizo (Active)	CHORIZO aims to improve the understanding between social norms, consumer behaviours and economic actor decisions and FLW generation and use this knowledge to improve the effectiveness of decision-making and engagement of food chain actors, towards zero food waste. The project’s main goal is to address existing research gaps and will use its outcomes to deliver and advance innovations helping actors to engage more effectively in food waste prevention and reduction activities.	Food waste, Policy impact, Circular economy, social norms	CSCP	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6	CHORIZO aims to improve the understanding of how social norms influence behaviour and FLW generation and use this knowledge to improve the effectiveness of decision-making and engagement of food chain actors towards zero FLW. PRECIOUS will link to the CHORIZO-identified FLWPR actions and create synergies in its stakeholder engagement activities.

FSC stage	Project	Description	Keywords	Partners involved	Relevant for WP	Engagement entry points
Non-food	CO2NSTRUCT (Active)	The EU-funded CO2NSTRUCT project will apply the TIMES energy-climate mitigation model as a proxy model to shift climate mitigation models from linear to circular. The focus will be on six carbon-intensive construction materials – steel, cement, brick, glass, wood, and insulation – to map six value chains with explicit feedback loops and quantified rebound effects, key to circular economy practices. TIMES will run several circular scenarios. Outcomes will be translated into useful and effective policy support information.	Circular economy, Climate mitigation, Policy impact, modelling	None	WP1	WP1 has established collaboration with the CO2NSTRUCT project to collaborate on methodologies for macroeconomic models.
Primary Production	COFRESH (Inactive)	The CO-FRESH project aimed to provide techniques, tools and insights on how to make agri-food value chains more environmentally sustainable, socio-economically balanced and economically competitive.	Policy impact, Societal impact, Biodiversity conservation	None	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	The techniques, tools, and insights developed for the re-design of agri-food value chains can be leveraged in PRECIOUS. Their use of pilots to inform their approaches can be examined for application in PRECIOUS.
Intermediate value chain	FAIRCHAIN (Inactive)	Innovative technological, organisational and social solutions for FAIRer dairy, fruit and vegetable value CHAINS: The main goal of FAIRCHAIN is to test, pilot and demonstrate recently developed technological, organisational and social innovations, realising a shift up to TRL7 and enabling small and mid-sized actors to scale-up and expand the production of affordable nutritious food in competitive intermediate food value chains.	Societal impact, Policy impact, Circular economy, digital innovation	None	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6	FAIRCHAIN also addressed fruit and vegetable sectors. Tools developed in FAIRCHAIN can inform the development of tools in PRECIOUS.
Primary Production	FOLOU (Active)	In line with the EU Green Deal and the Farm to Fork strategy, FOLOU is willing to contribute to unlock the systemic transition of EU food systems by setting up the necessary mechanisms to: Measure and estimate food losses at primary production stage, encompassing agriculture, aquaculture, and fisheries; monitor and report food losses at Member States and European levels; assess the magnitude and impact of Food Losses, and identify its key drivers.	Food waste	None	WP1, WP2, WP4, WP5	Tools developed in FOLOU can inform the development of tools in PRECIOUS, and vice versa.
Full food supply chain	FoodDataQuest (Active)	FoodDataQuest aims to co-create and test cutting-edge data-driven solutions powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms following a multi-actor approach, in order to provide the EU food chain stakeholders with increased insights and enhance the transition towards sustainable healthy diets. These innovations aim to optimize operations, minimize waste, and foster transparency throughout the food chain, all while empowering consumers to make healthier and more sustainable choices.	Food waste, Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment	None	WP1, WP2, WP4	The methodological framework developed in FoodDataQuest can inform PRECIOUS FLW tool development, and vice versa. Further, the testing of this framework in FoodDataQuest's 4 use cases can inform the approach taken for PRECIOUS UCs, CoPs and CRNs.
Full food supply chain	FOODGUARD (Active)	FOODGUARD aims to develop and demonstrate co-created solutions that will support innovations and advances based on the microbiome, microbial activities, and technology hubs to address food, health, economic, and environmental challenges. The envisioned approach consists of a framework of toolsets and methodologies to provide sustainable solutions in food processing, packaging, and across the food value chain to address food shelf-life increase & waste reduction holistically.	Food waste, Policy impact, Societal impact, microbiome	ASIN-CAR	All	Tools developed in FOODGUARD can inform the development of tools in PRECIOUS, and vice versa.

FSC stage	Project	Description	Keywords	Partners involved	Relevant for WP	Engagement entry points
Full food supply chain	FOODRUS (Inactive)	FOODRUS worked to tackle the food waste and losses by creating resilient food systems across nine European regions. To achieve this, the project tested 23 circular solutions through diverse forms of collaborative innovation, including: technological (blockchain solutions to manage food losses and waste), social (educational materials and citizen science activities to promote sustainable consumption habits), organisational (last mile networks to foster local consumption and donation), and fiscal (new ‘Pay As You Throw’ schemes). These innovative solutions will empower and engage all actors in local food systems, from farmers to end-consumers and everyone in between, to build a multi-actor alliance to tackle the challenge of food loss and waste.	Food waste	University of Deusto; Greenovate! Europe	All	A key element is the implementation of ICT tools for the quantification and monitoring of generated FLW along the entire agri-food chain. PRECIOUS suite will be built on this platform technology as a digital enabler that integrates its tools and data sources. PRECIOUS will also take advantage of the applicable solutions already developed in FOODRUS as is the case of the FLW quantification tools.
Primary production	LIAISON (Inactive)	LIAISON aims to make a significant and meaningful contribution to optimising interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of EU policies to speed up innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. LIAISON will produce practice-ready methods, protocols and tools, co-designed in processes involving the target users themselves. These include participatory tools for co-creation and co-learning, for networking, communication and dissemination, impact assessment tools, and methodologies and tools for self-evaluation. An Interactive Online System will help innovation actors to access these. LIAISON will develop detailed best practices and approaches for H2020 multi-actor projects, Thematic Networks, Operational Groups and other interactive innovation approaches that contribute to the implementation of EIP-Agri.	Interactive multi-actor agriculture, rural development policy, policy instrument, Common Agricultural Policy, European Innovation Partnership, social innovation	None	WP3, WP5, WP6	H2020-LIAISON aims to enhance interactive innovation approaches and the implementation of EU policies to expedite innovation in agriculture, forestry, and rural areas. PRECIOUS will take advantage of the knowledge generated regarding co-innovation with practitioners. The “How to” guidelines will be used as a reference.
Full food supply chain	LOWINFOOD (Active)	LOWINFOOD is focusing on the first levels of food waste hierarchy, that is, on prevention and reuse. The innovations that have been selected for the project are designed among promising solutions that have already been developed and tested by some partners and include technological tools and devices as well as organizational and managerial solutions.	Food waste, Circular economy, Societal impact, Digitalisation	None	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6	WP2 Innovations against loss of fruits and vegetables relevant for several of the PRECIOUS WPs. LOWINFOOD also focuses on at home consumption (household level) in their WP5, relevant for WP6 considerations.
Processing and Manufacturing	MAGNO (Inactive)	MAGNO aimed to analyse and determine the best food packaging manufacturing strategies. This includes the study of different raw materials and alternatives to fossil-based materials, design options, production routes and the approaches that exist to reduce waste generation during manufacture for a more efficient and environmentally friendly food packaging manufacturing practices.	Food waste, Societal impact, Policy impact, food packaging	None	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Best practices for food packaging manufacturing strategies can be utilised to reduce FLW in the PRECIOUS UCs.
Full food supply chain	PLOUTOS (Inactive)	Ploutos aims to create opportunities for changes that can rebalance the value chain in the agri-food system towards a more environmentally, socially and economically sustainable system. Until recently approaches to the agri-food system focused on narrow segments of the overall value chain. Ploutos will take a systems-based approach looking at the overall impact of changes at any point in the value chain, thereby enabling a more comprehensive and in depth understanding. To achieve that Ploutos will use the Sustainable Innovative Framework!	Agri-food system	None	All	The pilot projects and policy recommendations can inform the PRECIOUS approach.
Full food supply chain	PREMIERE (Inactive)	The Horizon Europe project PREMIERE was dedicated to improving the multi-actor approach implementation via the support to proposal preparation, notably consortium building and the development of practical tools to boost co-creation. As part of the multi-actor approach support, it analysed the role of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups in Horizon projects.	Multi-actor, agriculture, food, farming, bioeconomy, rural sectors	None	WP1, WP5, WP6	A participation in a survey offered by the PRECIOUS project lead served as an entry point towards collaboration. The project’s focus on co-creation and multi-actor approaches can be another entry point for WP6.

FSC stage	Project	Description	Keywords	Partners involved	Relevant for WP	Engagement entry points
Primary production	QuantiFarm (Active)	QuantiFarm focuses on supporting the further deployment of digital technology solutions in agriculture and food production (DATs) as key enablers for enhancing the sustainability performance and competitiveness of the agricultural sector.	Agriculture, digital solutions	None	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	QuantiFarm's toolkit can inform the PRECIOUS approach, particularly regarding the engagement of farmers.
Non-food	REBOUNDLESS (Active)	Towards the prevention of rebound effects within complex socio-technical systems: The EU-funded REBOUNDLESS project will explore the rebound effect mechanisms triggered by sustainable design strategies and create simulation models and design strategies to enable the 'reboundless' design of sustainable systems.	GHG emissions, rebound effects, sustainable design, system dynamics, design science, eco-design	None	WP1	The findings from REBOUNDLESS can inform PRECIOUS work on the rebound effect assessment carried out in task 1.5, and PRECIOUS findings can inform REBOUNDLESS.
Full food supply chain	REFRESH (Inactive)	The project took an innovative, systemic approach to curb food waste through a holistic "Framework for Action". REFRESH built on and went beyond existing initiatives to develop, evaluate, and ensure the spread of social, technological, and organisational insights and practices related to food waste. This was underpinned with guidance to legislators and policy makers to help support effective governance to tackle food waste.	Food waste, Policy impact	CSCP	All	The aim of the project was to contribute towards the objective of reducing FLW across the EU by 30% by 2025 and maximizing the value from unavoidable FLW and packaging materials. PRECIOUS will use its systemic approach to enrol businesses, consumers, and public authorities.
Full food supply chain	Rosetta (Active)	ROSETTA aims to revolutionise the food waste landscape linked to marketing standards, while also proposing and validating alternative marketing pathways for the effective utilisation of suboptimal foods, fostering sustainability and resource optimisation.	Policy impact, Societal impact, marketing standard	UNIMOS Alliance	WP1, WP3, WP5	ROSETTA has forged alliances with producers, logistics experts, processors, and consumers across various sectors including agri-food (meat, dairy, fruits & vegetables, cereals), bioeconomy, and related industries, that will be further built on in PRECIOUS.
Full food supply chain	SecureFood (Active)	The ultimate goal of SecureFood is to create an ecosystem of scientific knowledge, collaborative processes, and digital tools that contribute to evidence-based insights on risks and vulnerabilities in different food value chains. Focusing on key sectors such as grain, fruits and vegetables, fish and aquaculture products, and milk and dairy products, the project aims to safeguard food security both before and during crises.	Biodiversity conservation, Circular economy, food systems	None	All	The SecureFood ecosystem of scientific knowledge, collaborative processes, and digital tools can be leveraged to inform approaches in PRECIOUS.
Primary Production	Sisters (Active)	The SISTERS project aims to reduce food loss and waste in the main stages of the Food Value Chain in Europe through innovations targeted to each stage of the chain: New tools for primary producers for promoting direct and Short Chain sales (farmers); new technological innovations in packaging for processors and retailers; and awareness campaigns for retailers and consumers on food loss and waste.	Food waste, Societal impact, Circular economy, sustainable agriculture	None	WP1, WP2, WP4, WP5	Tools developed in Sisters can inform the development of tools in PRECIOUS, and vice versa.
Full food supply chain	SOSFood (Active)	SOSFood will use data-exploitation and AI-based technologies to provide a holistic and comprehensive image of the EU food system and develop tailored predictive tools to support well-informed decisions of all stakeholders of the food chain, with a multi-factorial, multi-actor and multi-scale approach, thanks to its multidisciplinary consortium of experts, from private and public sectors, academia research and food system representatives (consumers, producers and industries).	Food waste, Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment	None	WP1, WP2, WP4	Tools developed in SOSFood can inform the development of tools in PRECIOUS, and vice versa.

FSC stage	Project	Description	Keywords	Partners involved	Relevant for WP	Engagement entry points
Waste	SPRINT (Active)	<p>SPRINT is an EU-funded project that aims to reduce consumer food waste through evidence-based strategies. These strategies aim to improve economic, social and environmental performance, by combining technological tools with actions that change the choices available to consumers.</p> <p>The project will use a multi-stakeholder approach to analyse, co-create, implement and evaluate interventions in three pilot contexts: hotel restaurants, supermarkets and households in Spain.</p> <p>In addition, SPRINT will promote collaboration and develop educational resources to facilitate food waste reduction contributing to the formulation of efficient public policies and ensuring long-term sustainability.</p>	Food waste	ASIN-CAR	WP3, WP6	SPRINT's work can inform the PRECIOUS approach with strategies to engage the household level, if this direction is sought within the CoPs and CRNs.
Waste	ToNoWaste (Active)	ToNoWaste mission is to encourage actors in European food systems using science and evidence-based tools and lessons learned to make better decisions toward a more sustainable food production and consumption patterns.	Food waste	UJI, UDeusto	WP1, WP2, WP4, WP5	ToNoWaste proposes a sustainability assessment framework embedded in an ICT tool for developing FLWPR actions, given social, technical, environmental, economic, political, legal, ethical and demographic drivers and hindrances. PRECIOUS will use this platform technology to enable better decisions for more sustainable food production and consumption patterns.
Waste value chain	Waste4Think (Inactive)	The main objective of this project is to move forward the current waste management practices into a circular economy motto, demonstrating the value of integrating and validating a set of 20 eco-innovative solutions that cover all the waste value chain. The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a holistic waste data management methodology, and will be demonstrated in 4 complementary urban areas in Europe.	Recycling, governance, NGOs, business models, sustainable economy	UDeusto	WP1, WP2, WP4, WP7	W4T aims to move forward the current waste management practices into a circular economy motto, demonstrating the value of integrating and validating a set of 20 eco-innovative solutions that cover the entire waste value chain, enhanced by a holistic waste data management methodology. PRECIOUS will use this platform to enhance decision-making for fostering a more sustainable food system.
Full food supply chain	Wasteless (Active)	Wasteless is an applied research project, which aims to measure and monitor food losses and waste in the EU. The WASTELESS project will develop and test a mix of innovative tools and methodologies for Food Loss and Waste (FLW) measurement and monitoring, will recommend a harmonised methodological Framework for FLW quantification, and will develop a decision support systemic Toolbox targeting all food value chain stakeholders. Additionally, WASTELESS will carry on research activities concerning innovative processes and streams to valorise unavoidable FLW.	Food waste	None	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Tools developed in Wasteless can inform the development of tools in PRECIOUS, and vice versa.
Waste	WasteWise (Active)	<p>A Transformative Step Towards Reducing Food Waste in Europe</p> <p>Food waste prevention and reduction stand at the forefront of the European Green Deal and of the Farm-to-Fork strategy, aimed at fostering a fair, healthy, and sustainable food system. The EU is committed to reduce food waste per capita by 30% at retail and consumer level by 2030, and to reduce food losses along the food production and supply chain. WASTEWISE project will contribute to meet such targets. WASTEWISE project commits to design realistic pathways for food waste prevention and reduction to deliver co-benefits for climate change mitigation and biodiversity. The project also evaluates the nutritional losses and overall socio-economic rebound effects of prevention and reduction.</p>	Food waste, Policy impact, Circular economy, rebound effects	None	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	There is potential to collaborate on data and testing within UCs and CRNs. Initial conversations on collaboration around gathering data from companies in the meat sector were initiated in December 2024, to be further followed.

FSC stage	Project	Description	Keywords	Partners involved	Relevant for WP	Engagement entry points
Full food supply chain	Watson (Active)	Watson’s goal is to make food chains more sustainable by reducing food fraud and improving transparency. Watson is doing so through innovations that: Enhance track-and-trace mechanisms, ensuring food products contain accurate, real-time information throughout their journey. Equip authorities and policymakers with the data and insights they need to monitor the entire food supply chain. Increase consumer awareness of food safety, promoting healthier lifestyles and supporting the development of greener, more sustainable food ecosystems.	Agri-food	ASIN-CAR	WP1, WP2, WP4	Watsons digital technology architecture can inform PRECIOUS tool development.
Waste	ZeroW (Active)	ZeroW will provide credible solutions for significantly reducing FLW, involving all actors in the food system in a collaborative framework, to accelerate the just transition to a social, economic and environmentally sustainable food system for all.	Food waste, Climate change mitigation, Policy impact, GHG emissions	AgriFood Lithuania ASIN-CAR		ZeroW aims to establish as a major driving force in reducing FLW by employing systemic innovation, thus supporting the dual ambition: to halve FLW by 2030 and ensure the enabling conditions for near-zero FLW by 2050. PRECIOUS will use the generated knowledge and its systemic approach to enrol businesses, consumers, and public authorities.

Building on this mapping of European projects, section 5.3.4 outlines engagement formats for different engagement levels.

4.3. European platforms mapping and engagement entry points

To further enhance the dissemination of PRECIOUS activities and results, relevant European platforms are mapped in Table 3 below, with engagement entry points. The list of European platforms is also available as a ‘living document’ in the shared file location for additions by consortium partners.

Table 3: Mapping of European platforms and engagement entry points.

Platform	Description	Keywords	Relevant for WP	How to engage
EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste	The EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste (FLW) was established in 2016, bringing together EU institutions, experts from the EU countries, international organisations and relevant stakeholders selected through an open call for applications. The Platform aims to support all actors in: defining measures needed to prevent food waste; sharing best practices; and evaluating progress made over time.	Food waste	All, WP7	Disseminate PRECIOUS communications, events and results. A detailed engagement plan will be developed under Task 6.4.
EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub	The EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub is a "one-stop-shop" for stakeholders active in the area of food loss and waste prevention and reduction.	Food waste	All, WP7	Feature PRECIOUS and disseminate PRECIOUS communications, events and results.
Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform	Online environment with the purpose of ensuring the sustainability of knowledge from European projects in the field of innovative food systems by sharing their activities and results, even after the end of projects.	Food system	All, WP7	Feature PRECIOUS and disseminate PRECIOUS communications, events and results.
EU-Farmbook	Gathering and sharing agriculture and forestry knowledge based on cocreation approach and built on EURAKNOS and EUREKA outputs.	Agriculture, forestry	All, WP7	Dissemination of project results relevant for agricultural sector.
European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	Virtual open space whose aim is to promote the transition to a circular economy by facilitating policy dialogue among stakeholders, by disseminating good practices, strategies and voluntary commitments, and by providing information on the circular economy and related activities.	Circular economy, Policy impact, Societal impact	WP5, WP7	Disseminate PRECIOUS communications, events and results to policymakers.

Platform	Description	Keywords	Relevant for WP	How to engage
Food2030 online platform	Common platform for all projects, partnerships, networks, and living labs working on transforming the food system for the benefit of the people and the planet.		All, WP7	Project collaboration network, Connected Lab Network, Sustainable Food System Network
ECEMF	ECEMF is a Horizon 2020 funded project whose aim is to establish a European forum for energy and climate researchers and policy makers to achieve climate neutrality. ECEMF will inform future energy and climate policies at national and European level and present a more coherent, unified evidence base that will, in turn, form a concrete basis for action by policy makers. The European Climate and Energy Modelling Platform (ECEMP) is the annual conference, co-organized by the ECEMF and other EC projects (formerly called EMP-E) for exchanging research, development and practice of energy and climate modelling in Europe.	Climate change mitigation, Climate change adaptation, GHG emissions	WP1, WP2, WP4, WP5, WP7	Relevant for modelling tasks, co-developing policy briefs and project results dissemination.
EU CAP Network (EIP-AGRI Operational Groups)	National CAP Networks, organisations, administrations, researchers, entrepreneurs and practitioners can share knowledge and information (e.g. via peer-to-peer learning and good practices) about agriculture and rural policy.	Agriculture, rural policy	All, WP7	Dissemination of project results relevant for agricultural sector.
Biorefine Cluster Europe	The Biorefine Cluster Europe interconnects projects and people within the domain of biobased resource recovery, striving to contribute to a more sustainable resource management in the framework of circular economy systems.	Circular economy, Biodiversity conservation, Food waste	WP1, WP2, WP3	Engaging with this cluster could be relevant for by-products and waste revalorization in the UCs.

The above mapping indicates first entry points. Building on this, and Deliverable D7.9 – *Plan for Exploitation, dissemination and communication*, Greenovate! Europe, with the support of CSCP and other project partners, will define a joint work plan detailing activities related to communications as well as dissemination of publications and participation in events.

5. Stakeholder engagement

Food loss and waste (FLW) is an issue that arises across the food supply chain that requires a systemic approach and is dependent on the engagement and buy-in of a vast array of stakeholders. Implementing changes across a whole supply chain is complex. For sustained change, it is important to involve all key actors and to understand their interests, motivations, drivers and needs; to tap into their knowledge and expertise; and to take them along the journey to change.

Stakeholder engagement is a structured approach where all relevant actors communicate frequently, foster trust among themselves, and collaborate to achieve shared objectives. Ideally, these stakeholders eventually take responsibility for the change and emerge as leaders in driving the transformation process. In the context of PRECIOUS, stakeholder engagement involves an ongoing and inclusive dialogue with key participants who can influence food loss and waste prevention and reduction (FLWPR) efforts, whether directly or indirectly.

5.1. Purpose and scope

Multi-stakeholder engagement is an integral part of the PRECIOUS approach. PRECIOUS will foster collaboration among different stakeholders across the full supply chain to implement the proposed solutions. By leveraging interactions among diverse stakeholders, PRECIOUS aims to generate, share, and apply knowledge on Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Reduction (FLWPR) actions.

In the PRECIOUS approach, stakeholders are actively involved in co-creating solutions that align with their needs through the formation of Communities of Practice (CoP) in each of the Use Cases (UCs) in Greece and Spain. Furthermore, the Co-Creation and Replication Nodes (CRNs) in Poland, Lithuania, and Hungary will play an important role in co-creation activities, enabling the replication of solutions beyond the initial implementation in the UCs. Their involvement will also support the dissemination of PRECIOUS results across Europe. This collaborative effort will enable the development of a tailored and effective sustainable FLWPR strategy. The objective of this initial engagement plan is to provide guidelines for engaging relevant actors in in PRECIOUS across the food supply chain.

5.2. Roles and responsibilities

Stakeholder engagement is a shared responsibility among all partners in PRECIOUS. Effective engagement is key to meeting the project's objectives and goals; therefore, all partners are required to consider when, how and why to engage stakeholders for successful project implementation. Through WP6 the CSCP has a coordinating role in supporting effective stakeholder engagement, and through Task 6.5 in particular, CSCP and EIT Food provide support to all Work Packages to identify the most suitable and effective stakeholder engagement formats and tools to reach the tasks' objectives.

The Use Cases and CoPs, as well as the CRNs are particularly dependent on the engagement of stakeholders, therefore the local partners have contributed to the stakeholder analysis by providing a mapping of their local stakeholders. Following the stakeholder analysis provided above, and the guidance and tools for creating engagement plans shared in subsequent sections, local partners are responsible to develop stakeholder engagement plans for their locations with the support of CSCP as well as other partners who are developing the measures to be tested through the UCs, CoPs and CRNs. These plans will be further developed and specified in D6.2 – *CoP governance framework* and inform the Replication Protocol that will be authored by EIT Food to guide the activities in the CRNs.

5.3. Initial engagement plan

Based on the preceding stakeholder analysis, the initial engagement plan will now be outlined for the Use Cases, the Co-creation and Replication Nodes, as well as EU stakeholders and projects.

5.3.1. Methodology

To develop the initial engagement plan, the stakeholder analysis in the first part of this document informed the recommendations in the sections to follow. Further, the framework for the initial engagement plan has been influenced by the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2) spectrum. The IAP2 spectrum is an internationally recognised framework, designed to help select the appropriate level of participation required to achieve the objectives of different stakeholder activities (IAP2, 2024). Table 4 shows the spectrum adapted for PRECIOUS purposes. The level of engagement increases from left to right in the table: ‘Inform’ represents the lowest level of engagement, while ‘Empower’ represents the highest level of engagement. The goal of stakeholder engagement and the promise implicitly made to the stakeholders at each level are detailed in the table.

Table 4: The framework used to identify the appropriate level of engagement, adapted from the IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation.

	INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	EMPOWER
Stakeholder participation goal	Stakeholders are provided with information about the project, but not directly involved (e.g. website, communications, informative webinars).	Stakeholders are consulted for information or feedback, but with little interaction (e.g. a survey, interactive webinar).	Stakeholders are involved in the project to a greater extent (e.g. provision of data) throughout the project. However, decision-making remains within the project team.	Stakeholders are invited to collaborate to a greater extent, work nearly as partners in the project.	Stakeholders are given the tools and the decision-making power they need to implement changes themselves.
Promise made to stakeholders	We will keep you informed.	We will keep you informed, listen to and acknowledge concerns and aspirations, and provide feedback.	We will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide Feedback.	We will look to you for advice and incorporate your advice and Recommendations.	We will provide advice and assistance.

5.3.2. Engagement of Use Cases and CRNS stakeholders

5.3.2.1. Next steps for the engagement plan for UCs and CRNs

Following the Engagement Decision Points and the Engagement Entry Points recommended throughout sections 3.2 to 3.6, the next steps to prepare for defining the engagement plan are the following:

Common Next Steps for Engagement Plans

To effectively prepare for defining the engagement plans across all locations, the following common steps should be taken:

- **Defining Scope and Themes:** Determine the focus areas based on the needs of the Use Cases, relevant PRECIOUS WPs, and the mapped stakeholders, in collaboration with project partners and supported by CSCP.
- **Identifying and Engaging Stakeholders:** Assess which stakeholders to involve and whether to expand participation by including additional relevant actors.
- **Selection Considerations:** When choosing stakeholders, take into account influence, interest rankings, food waste prevention engagement levels, and the sector-specific impact on FLWPR.
- **Recruitment Strategies:** Highlight key aspects that respond to stakeholders' needs and interests, such as cross-stage learning, exchange opportunities, corporate social responsibility, and financial benefits.

Location-Specific Insights

- **Greek CoP:**
 - Consider including additional stakeholders from food services and households.
 - Recruitment should emphasize cross-stage learning, CSR, and financial benefits.
- **Spanish CoP:**
 - Expand the diverse stakeholder group by including actors with cross-stage dependence.
 - Engagement arguments should be tailored to key motivators of each supply chain stage.
- **Hungarian CRN:**
 - Many stakeholders contribute to FLW but have limited awareness and action.
 - Potential inclusion of packaging, retail, redistribution, and non-food actors.
 - Local engagement is challenging due to weak ties with food supply chain actors; steps should be taken to mitigate this risk.
- **Lithuanian CRN:**
 - Primary production and processing actors dominate, enabling strong multiplier effects.
 - Consider expanding to wholesale and food service sectors.
 - Potential for the CRN to act as a national FLWPR collaborative platform.
- **Polish CRN:**
 - Focus could be on redistribution or on primary production and processing to replicate Use Case results.
 - Address key engagement barriers: accountability concerns, consumer acceptance, and cross-stage collaboration.
 - Expand to include public stakeholders at regional and local levels, and household actors.
 - Emphasize learning, exchange, and CSR benefits when recruiting stakeholders.

5.3.3. Engagement levels for further actors

5.3.3.1. Engagement levels for European stakeholders

Following the Engagement Entry Points recommended in Chapter 4.1, European stakeholders can be engaged in PRECIOUS at the following engagement levels:

Table 5: Engagement levels for European stakeholders.

	Inform	Consult	Involve	Collaborate	Empower
Description	Provide EU stakeholders with relevant updates about PRECIOUS, including results, methodologies, and key findings.	Gather feedback and insights from EU policymakers, institutions, food related platforms, and industry associations to ensure PRECIOUS aligns with existing policies and market needs.	Actively involve EU stakeholders by integrating their expertise, data, insights, or policy initiatives into PRECIOUS activities.	Work closely with EU policymakers, institutions, and industry associations, integrating their tools, models, and policy frameworks into PRECIOUS activities.	Provide EU stakeholders with the tools, methodologies, and decision-making power to implement and scale up FLW prevention actions independently.
Stakeholder motivations	Stay informed about FLW research and policy developments, identify synergies with ongoing EU initiatives and regulations, gain insights that could inform decision-making.	Gain early access to project findings and contribute to shaping them. Share concerns and recommendations for more effective FLWPR strategies. Influence project outcomes to ensure alignment with regulatory and industry needs.	Shape the development of standardised methodologies for FLW reduction. Align food waste prevention efforts across the EU. Access to project insights for policy and industry strategy development.	Strengthen the impact of their own initiatives and enhance visibility of their efforts in FLW prevention.	Implement tested and trialled approaches for FLWPR.
PRECIOUS offer	Clear and accessible communication of research findings, best practices, and policy developments. Evidence-based insights for decision-making in food waste prevention.	A platform for stakeholders to share their perspectives, knowledge, and policy needs.	Opportunities to align with EU-wide food waste strategies and their use towards net-zero goals. Access to a broader FLW data ecosystem and validated models.	A structured platform for cooperation on systemic FLW reduction. Collaboration on EU-level food waste reporting and standardization efforts. Integration of project findings into EU policy frameworks	Transferable tools, guidelines, and training materials that enable long-term systemic change. Support for integrating FLW strategies into national and EU-level regulations.

				(e.g. Farm to Fork Strategy).	
Engagement formats	Website updates, newsletters, social media posts, publicly available deliverables, informative webinars.	Online surveys, feedback forms, structured interviews, interactive webinars, dedicated stakeholder consultation workshops.	Collaboration on data sharing for FLWPR. Joint contribution to EU FLW policy recommendations.	Long-term partnerships, joint initiatives.	FLWPR Open Data tool suite, policy recommendations.
Responsibilities	WP and Task Leaders, in alignment with WP7.	WP and Task Leaders.	WP and Task Leaders.	WP and Task Leaders.	WP and Task Leaders.

5.3.4. Engagement levels for European Projects

Following the Engagement Entry Points recommended in Chapter 4.2, European projects can be engaged in PRECIOUS at the following engagement levels:

Table 6: Engagement levels for European projects.

	Inform	Consult	Involve	Collaborate	Empower
Description of Engagement Entry Points	Provide European projects with relevant updates about PRECIOUS, including results, methodologies, and key findings.	Gather insights and feedback from other European projects through structured interactions, ensuring their perspectives are considered.	Actively involve other European projects by integrating their expertise, methodologies, insights, or data into PRECIOUS, ensuring continuous collaboration.	Work closely with European projects, integrating their tools, models, and insights into PRECIOUS activities.	Provide European projects with the tools, methodologies, and decision-making power to implement and scale up FLW prevention actions independently.
European FWL projects' motivations	Stay informed about advancements in FLW reduction, explore synergies, and gain insights applicable to their own projects.	Share their own findings and contribute to shaping PRECIOUS outputs while ensuring alignment with existing initiatives.	Influence research directions, enhance their own project impact through shared knowledge and resources.	Strengthen their project outcomes through deeper integration and boost visibility.	Directly implement and sustain impactful solutions beyond their project's duration.
PRECIOUS offer to European FWL projects	Clear and accessible communication of research findings, best practices, and policy developments.	A platform for projects to provide input on methodologies, and exchange knowledge.	Access to a broader FLW data ecosystem, opportunities to align efforts for greater collective impact.	Cross-project cooperation for greater impact.	Transferable tools, guidelines, and training materials that enable long-term systemic change.
Engagement formats for European FWL projects	Website updates, newsletters, social media posts, publicly available deliverables, informative webinars.	Online surveys, feedback forms, structured interviews, interactive webinars.	Data sharing agreements, co-authored research papers, contribution to FLWPR tool suite.	Joint working groups, long-term partnerships, formal collaborations on policy impact.	Co-creation efforts, materials and access to data.
Relevant PRECIOUS tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP7 • All other WP and Task Leaders, in alignment with WP7. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1 • WP2 • T5.1. • T.7.1 • T7.3. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1 • WP2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T5.4. • T5.5. • T6.4. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T4.1. • T4.3.

5.4. Process to develop PRECIOUS engagement plans

Effectively engaging stakeholders is a dynamic and iterative process that requires careful planning, clear objectives, and continuous adaptation. This section outlines the key considerations for developing engagement plans, including the definition of priorities, key performance indicators (KPIs), and the timing of engagement decisions. A structured approach ensures that stakeholder interactions are meaningful, strategically aligned, and contribute to the project's overall impact.

Building on the stakeholder analysis, engagement decisions, entry points, and engagement levels identified earlier, the CSCP with the support of project partners will further refine the stakeholder engagement plans, particularly in the process of designing the CoPs and CRNs engagement. This involves detailing specific actions, identifying responsible actors, and ensuring alignment with the project's overarching objectives. The engagement process should be guided by a clear understanding of which stakeholders to engage, when to engage them, and the anticipated impact of these interactions.

To facilitate this process, the following template in Table 7 provides a structured framework for stakeholder engagement planning. It includes key guiding questions designed to support collaborative discussions, supporting partners to systematically define engagement strategies and maximise stakeholder involvement throughout the project lifecycle.

Table 7: Template to plan stakeholder engagement.

WP & Task	Time line	Meeti ng frequ ency	Objective of the activity	Description of engagement needs	Stakeholder groups to be engaged	Benefit for the stakeholder	Envisioned engagement formats	Follow-up activities
			Please briefly state the objective of the activity. What do you hope to achieve/what outcome are you envisioning from this activity?	Please state briefly what your engagement needs are and WHY you need to engage stakeholders.	Please list all stakeholder groups that should be engaged.	What will the stakeholder get out of the engagement (e.g. insights, exchange, visibility, etc.).	Consider the level of engagement (inform, consult, collaborate, etc.) Consider the engagement format (interview, workshop, etc.)	Consider which follow-up activities are needed, e.g. sharing the recording of a webinar, etc.

6. Next Steps to advance the PRECIOUS mission

The stakeholder mapping and initial engagement plan outlined in this document provide a foundational framework for advancing the PRECIOUS mission. By identifying key stakeholders, defining engagement priorities, and establishing entry points, we have set the course for meaningful interactions that will drive PRECIOUS objectives forward. This strategic approach not only enhances stakeholder collaboration but also ensures that the knowledge generated throughout the project is effectively disseminated and leveraged for broader impact.

Looking ahead, the engagement strategy for European projects and platforms will directly contribute to Deliverable D7.9 - Plan for Exploitation, dissemination and communication. Additionally, the engagement strategy for each CoP and CRN location will be further refined in the coming months in collaboration with project partners responsible to further develop the engagement plans, as well as incorporating insights gained from ongoing interactions and evolving project needs. The outcomes of these discussions will feed into Deliverable D6.2 - Communities of Practice and inform the development of the replication protocol led by EIT Food, ensuring a cohesive and well-integrated approach to stakeholder engagement.

7. References

Enserink, B., Bots, P., Van Daalen, E., Hermans, L., Koppenjan, J., Kortmann, R., Kwakkel, J., Slinger, J., Ruijgh Van Der Ploeg, T., & Thissen, W. (2022). *Policy Analysis of Multi-Actor Systems*. TU Delft OPEN Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5074/T.2022.004>

International Association for Public Participation. (IAP2). (2024). *IAP2 Spectrum of Participation*. Accessed March 5, 2025. https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.iap2.org/resource/resmgr/pillars/iap2_spectrum_2024.pdf

Annex 1

Stakeholder Mapping Template

The stakeholder mapping template was provided to the local partners. It spanned over 26 variables, of which 25 had to be filled in by the local partners. 22 of these variables asked questions about local stakeholders. Below, a list of the 26 variables is provided. If drop-down menus were provided to answer a question, these are listed as well. The template was developed and adapted by the WP6 lead, gathering feedback from members of WP1, WP3, and WP6.

To support the local partners in filling in this survey, they were provided with 2 additional rows of explanations about why each question is asked, and how they should answer each question. Further, the local partners were always able to reach out to the WP6 lead in case of questions.

Questions/Variables:

1. Unique ID (don't edit)
2. Author
3. Location
4. Stakeholder organisation [Free text answer]
5. Website of Stakeholder organisation [Free text answer]
6. How are you connected to the stakeholder?
 - 0 - No direct relationship so far
 - 1 - We communicate with each other occasionally.
 - 2 - We are in the same network / They are part of our network
 - 3 - We regularly work together
7. Which stage of the food supply chain is the stakeholder mostly active in?
 1. Primary Production
 - 2.1 Processing and Manufacturing
 - 2.2 Reprocessing
 - 2.3 Packaging
 - 3.1 Retail
 - 3.2 Wholesale
 - 3.3 Redistribution (food banks, apps, food sharing)
 - 3.4 Other forms of distribution
 4. Restaurants and food services
 5. Households
 - 6.1 Non-Food: End of Life (Disposal, Waste, Composting, Energy)
8. What is the geographic scope of this stakeholder's activities?
 - local
 - regional
 - national
 - European
 - International
9. Type of organisation: Please select the description that suits your stakeholder the most [Answer options based on NACE codes, local partners were provided with additional information about each answer]
 - 01.1 Growing of non-perennial crops(en)
 - 01.2 Growing of perennial crops(en)
 - 01.3 Plant propagation(en)

01.4 Animal production(en)
01.5 Mixed farming(en)
01.6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities(en)
01.7 Hunting, trapping and related service activities(en)
03 Fishing and aquaculture(en)
03.1 Fishing(en)
03.2 Aquaculture(en)
08.91 Mining of chemical and fertiliser minerals(en)
10.1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products(en)
10.2 Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs(en)
10.3 Processing and preserving of fruit and vegetables(en)
10.4 Manufacture of vegetable and animal oils and fats(en)
10.5 Manufacture of dairy products and edible ice(en)
10.6 Manufacture of grain mill products, starches and starch products(en)
10.7 Manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products(en)
10.8 Manufacture of other food products(en)
10.9 Manufacture of prepared animal feeds(en)
11.0 Manufacture of beverages(en)
20 Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products(en)
36 Water collection, treatment and supply
37 Sewage
38 Waste collection, recovery and disposal activities
46.1 Wholesale on a fee or contract basis(en)
46.2 Wholesale of agricultural raw materials and live animals (en)
46.3 Wholesale of food, beverages and tobacco (en)
46.5 Wholesale of information and communication equipment (en)
46.6 Wholesale of other machinery, equipment and supplies (en)
47.1 Non-specialised retail sale(en)
47.2 Retail sale of food, beverages and tobacco(en)
47.5 Retail sale of other household equipment(en)
47.6 Retail sale of cultural and recreational goods(en)
52 Warehousing, storage and support activities for transportation(en) (logistics)
55.1 Hotels and similar accommodation(en)
55.2 Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (en)
55.9 Other accommodation(en)
56.1 Restaurants and mobile food service activities(en)
56.2 Event catering, contract catering service activities and other food service activities(en)
56.3 Beverage serving activities(en)
64 Financial and Insurance activities
72 Scientific research and development(en)
73.1 Advertising(en)
73.2 Market research and public opinion polling(en)
73.3 Public relations and communication activities (NGOs, Consulting, advocates)
84.1 Administration of the State and the economic, social and environmental policies of the community(en)
85 Education
94.1 Activities of business, employers and professional membership organisations (Farmer associations, Professional associations, interest groups)

- 94.2 Activities of trade unions
- 94.91 Activities of religious organisations(en)
- 94.92 Activities of political organisations(en)
- Food services in non-food businesses (healthcare, education, staff, travel)
- Food sharing networks, apps & co
- Households
- Food Banks (non-religious)
- Private Organic Standardization Organisation/ Labelling Organisation
- Supplier for Agricultural Sector
- X OTHER

10. What are the stakeholder's main activities? Please describe briefly so we can understand their role. [Free text answer]
11. Which of these sentences best describes their engagement towards food waste reduction so far?
 - 1 - Food waste is not important to them, and they do not act to reduce it.
 - 2 - Food waste is very low on their agenda, and they do not act to reduce it.
 - 3 - Food waste is very low on their agenda, but their decisions affect the amount of food waste.
 - 4 - Food waste is a relevant topic for them, but they do not actively act to reduce it.
 - 5 - Food waste is a relevant topic for them, and they do act to reduce it to a limited extent.
 - 6 - Food waste is very relevant for them, and they are actively reducing it.
 - 7 - Food waste is a central issue for them and their organisation actively fights it.
12. How interested is the stakeholder in food loss and waste prevention and reduction actions? (1-10, 10 = highest)
 - 1
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - 10
13. How does this stakeholder contribute to food loss and waste?
 - 1 - They contribute to food waste as a loss or waste of their operations.
 - 2 - They set or enforce regulations that lead to loss or waste for others.
 - 3 - They provide technological solutions to reduce food waste.
 - 4 - Their operations reduce food waste, e.g. via redistribution.
 - 5 - None of the above.
14. How does this stakeholder contribute to food waste? Please provide us with some additional insights so we can understand their role. [Free text answer]
15. How relevant is this stakeholder to achieve significant reduction in FLW AND/OR rebound effects? (1-10, 10 = highest)
 - 1
 - 2
 - 3

- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10

16. Why did you assign this relevance rating to the stakeholder? Please describe briefly. [Free text answer]
17. How does food loss and waste reduction and prevention affect the operations of the stakeholder?
- 1 - Positive (FLWPR benefits their operations)
 - 2 - Neutral (FLWPR does not affect their operations)
 - 3 - Negative (FLWPR conflicts their operations)
 - 4 - Unclear
18. Why did you select this answer? Please briefly explain. [Free text answer]
19. Which argument might be most convincing to recruit the stakeholder?
- Achieving policy objectives (social, environmental, or other)
 - Collecting cross-sectoral input
 - Good for corporate social responsibility
 - High return on investment
 - Learning best practices
 - None of the above
 - Platform for advocacy
 - Platform for knowledge exchange / learning
 - Platform to solve conflicts / create synergies
 - Reduced (financial) losses
20. Why do you think this argument might be convincing for them? [Free text answer]
21. Which main barrier does the stakeholder experience when trying to reduce food waste? (select the most relevant one)
- Acting alone creates disadvantage
 - Behavioural challenges
 - Contractual restrictions
 - Lack of agency
 - Lack of consumer acceptance
 - Lack of cross-sectoral collaboration
 - Lack of demand
 - Lack of financial resources
 - Lack of knowledge
 - Product standards
 - Technological challenges
 - Legal challenges
 - Marketing challenges
 - Bureaucratic challenges
 - Uneconomical
 - Other / none of the above
22. Why do you think this might be a relevant barrier for the stakeholder to reduce or prevent FLW? [Free text answer]

23. What specific needs does this stakeholder have concerning food loss and waste prevention and reduction? [Free text answer]
24. To what degree are their challenges caused by cross-sectoral AND/OR cross-supply-chain issues? (1-10, 10 = highest)
- 1
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - 10
25. Which other stakeholders does this stakeholder frequently collaborate with or depend on? [Free text answer]
26. Do you have any additional comments or remarks about this stakeholder or your previous answers? [Free text answer]

